

**THE DILEMMA OF DISENGAGEMENT: CORPORATE EXIT FROM MYANMAR
AND IMPLICATIONS FOR BUSINESS-FOR-PEACE (B4P) THEORY**

Building a Framework for Responsible Exit through Ethical Decision-Making and Context-
Sensitive Analysis

by

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ABSTRACT

THE DILEMMA OF DISENGAGEMENT: CORPORATE EXIT FROM MYANMAR AND IMPLICATIONS FOR BUSINESS-FOR-PEACE (B4P) THEORY

Building a Framework for Responsible Exit through Ethical Decision-Making and Context-Sensitive Analysis

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This study begins from the recognition that peace is not a unilateral concept but a multi-layered and complex phenomenon. The 2021 military coup in Myanmar presented an unprecedented ethical challenge to multinational corporations. The risk of providing financial resources to an illegitimate regime has been exponentially aggravated, while withdrawal threatened severe economic harm to local workers and communities. This scenario fundamentally undermined the ‘presence assumption’ of Business-for-Peace (B4P) theory as the optimistic belief that corporate presence itself contributes positively to peace.

Accordingly, instead of employing a singular theoretical lens, this analysis focuses on the Myanmar case in its multidimensional perspective, which integrates B4P theory, Jones’s moral intensity model, and responsible exit theory. The questions for the research work are: (1) How did Myanmar's political trajectory affect the ethical climate of corporate withdrawal

decisions? (2) How do Jones's six dimensions of moral intensity account for different responses of corporate reactions (immediate exit, slow withdrawal, ongoing presence)? (3) In response to this question of the consequences, what were the real impacts of various withdrawal strategies on local stakeholders? (4) Analyzing these findings, how a "Responsible Exit Framework" (REF) can be developed?

A qualitative document analysis was employed, drawing on corporate reports, international organization documents, NGO publications, and media sources. Where available, published interview data from academic studies and reports were incorporated into the analysis in order to explore qualitative data from Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis. The key findings indicate that the corporate withdrawal decisions were shaped by multiple dimensions of moral intensity, particularly magnitude of consequences, social consensus, and proximity, which interacted in complex ways to shape corporate responses. Secondly, the withdrawal method (immediate/gradual) and the time frame influenced the local stakeholders in a different way. Third, the companies belonging to the middle powers, including the Koreans, confronted ethical challenges not experienced by Western firms.

It provides a Responsible Exit Framework that can be applied not only for Myanmar but also as a practical perspective for corporate exit decisions with other conflict-affected countries like Ukraine and Ethiopia.

Keywords: Business-for-Peace (B4P), Responsible Exit, Moral Intensity, Myanmar Coup, State Capture, Middle Power Corporations, Ethical Decision-Making

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CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

Introduction

Over the past 20 years, the study of the role of business in conflict zones has steadily gained academic traction. Business-for-Peace (B4P), in particular, has received attention as it argues that businesses can positively contribute to peacebuilding beyond profit-making (Fort & Schipani, 2004; Miklian & Katsos, 2024). Many scholars and policymakers support the positive potential of corporate daily operations, such as job creation, economic development, and stakeholder engagement, to contribute to the reduction of conflict and social stability.

South Korean Corporations' Changing Situation

In this global conversation, Korea is now in a unique position. From being a recipient of international aid to becoming a donor state and now an important economic power in the world, the extent of Korean corporations working in conflict areas is gradually increasing. However, the development of ethical standards in response to this growth has been slow. Korean companies are also working in conflict-affected places like Myanmar, Vietnam, and Indonesia, but there are no established policy processes or mechanisms available for dealing with unexpected political disruptions.

Figure 1.1 Myanmar FDI Trend (2018-2025)

Myanmar's FDI peaked at 4.88 billion USD in 2019-20, but sharply declined after the 2021 military coup. It rebounded slightly to 1.64 billion USD in 2022-23, but has stagnated at around 660 million USD since 2023-24. This trend demonstrates that political instability continues to have a negative impact on foreign investment in Myanmar.

Source: DICA, KOTRA (2025)

Figure 1.2 Cumulative Investment in Myanmar by Country (as of Feb 2025)

Singapore is the largest foreign investor in Myanmar with cumulative investments of 26.5 billion USD, followed by China (22.0 billion USD) and Thailand (11.6 billion USD). Korea ranks sixth with 4.2 billion USD in cumulative investment, higher than Japan's 1.8 billion USD. Other countries and regions, including Hong Kong (10.0 billion USD) and the United Kingdom (7.4 billion USD), also maintain significant investment presence in Myanmar. This distribution reflects the dominant role of Asian neighbors in Myanmar's FDI landscape.

Source: Myanmar Investment Commission, DICA, KOTRA (2025)

Figure 1.3 Cumulative Investment in Myanmar by Sector (as of Feb 2025)

The oil and gas sector attracted the largest share of FDI during fiscal year 2024-25 (54%, 357 million USD), followed by manufacturing (23.2%, 153 million USD) and power (13.3%, 87.7 million USD). The transport and communications sector, which includes telecommunications companies such as Telenor, accounted for 8.7% (51.1 million USD) of total FDI. This concentration in resource and infrastructure sectors reflects Myanmar's long-standing

investment patterns.

Source: DICA, Frontier Myanmar (2025)

Questions and Controversy Raised by the Myanmar Coup

Companies within this perspective had to respond to the most basic questions raised by the military coup in Myanmar in February 2021. With the democratically elected government deposed and the military returning to power, multinational corporations that had ventured into Myanmar faced a serious ethical dilemma. Continuing operations could be seen as supporting the illegitimate regime through economic assistance, whereas withdrawal would cause significant harm to the local economy, affecting workers and communities. As Breen (2024, p. 291) explains, “the B4P model has been undertheorized in a world where the state is sometimes an instrument of violence and where companies have no easy way of acting ethically and with integrity toward their clients.” Unfortunately, the Myanmar case sharply revealed the limitations of the prevailing B4P theory.

A Conceptual Gap in the Concept of Responsible Exit

The literature so far has largely emphasized corporate 'entry' and 'operations', with 'exit' having been neglected in academic focus. Brenkert (2021, p. 537) highlighted this gap and suggested a need to expand the notion of responsible exit to account for "process, timing, and stakeholder involvement." However, research on their use in specific contexts, such as rapid-onset state capture (like Myanmar), is still lacking as it is an early-stage concept.

Necessity of the Study

In this context, the study seeks to examine several corporate exit options in relation to the Myanmar example and formulate a systematic plan for responsible exit based on this examination. It will also provide practical advice on how corporations from middle powers like Korea can approach similar situations in the future.

1.2 Problem Statement

A blindness of B4P theory: The 'presence assumption' problem

Over the last two decades, business-for-Peace (B4P) theory has contributed insightfully to understand how businesses are playing in peacebuilding. But this theory suffers from a huge blind spot: the naive assumption that corporate 'presence' invariably implies good outcomes—the 'presence assumption.' As Miklian and Katsos (2024, p. 118) criticize, B4P research has been "structurally fragmented through an overuse of success stories and corporate self-reports [and] methodologically constrained." As a consequence, analysis of what kind of negative effects companies might make in conflict situations has been neglected.

Theoretical Gap

The 2021 military coup in Myanmar exposed this theoretical dissonance. This presents the current multinational corporation with a question, when faced with a sudden political transformation, when:

If continuing operations: Risk that it indirectly incurs human rights abuses by subsidizing it (taxes, fees, licensing costs) the illegitimate military regime.

If withdrawing: Risk that they could create severe economic loss to local workers, suppliers and communities, and the risk that abandoned assets could be transferred to military or military-linked enterprises.

Analyzing this dilemma, Breen (2024, p. 298) cautions against "the suppression or even reappropriation of corporate peacebuilding when the state is the agent of conflict itself." This makes evident that the current B4P frameworks do not work in the unique context of state capture.

Academic attention has long been blind spot towards corporate exit. Exit has usually been viewed as failure or strategic retreat, and there has been limited research into the ethics of

exit. Brenkert (2021, p. 537) has emphasized the need for a responsible exit by introducing the idea of 'tragic ethical choices' (Brenkert), whereby "there's moral force to give weight to all the options out there, and the decision maker has to decide among unavoidable harms." But his model is still very early and there is no empirical research addressing how it might be applied specifically under the condition of rapid-onset state capture as seen in Myanmar.

Disconnect Between Theory and Practice

Jones's (1991) moral intensity model is a valuable theoretical framework to explain the effects of corporate exit decisions, yet research using it in the context of corporate exit decisions is limited. In contrast, the empirical studies of Myanmar case (Berman, 2022; Meyer & Thein, 2023) describe corporation decisions but do not provide systematic discussion of the relevant ethical reasoning processes for these decisions.

Particularity of Middle Power Corporations

In addition, the literature on these topics has largely been informed by the experience and perspective of Western multinational corporations. Middle powers corporations, including companies in Korea also encountered particular ethical dilemmas due to geographic proximity, a largely established history of economic relationship with Myanmar, and pressure exerted on civil society from the local authorities in comparison to that of Western firms. But studies showcasing this specific nature are practically non-existent.

Synthesis of Research Problems

As our discussion integrates, the following central question emerges:

“What does responsible exit mean, and how can we set up a framework to systematically support it in an ethical context whereby corporate presence is problematic?”

This study examines the Myanmar case to explore this question.

1.3 Research Questions and Hypotheses

1.3.1 Research Questions

RQ1 (Descriptive-Historical)

In what way do different historical trajectories of Myanmar's political development, characterized by decades of military rule, partial liberalization (2011-2020), and the 2021 coup, impact the ethical environment in which corporate withdrawal decisions were made and the actual corporate response patterns?

RQ2 (Analytical-Theoretical)

Using analysis of Jones's (1991) six dimensions of moral intensity, how do the divergent corporate responses to the Myanmar coup (immediate exit, gradual withdrawal, continued presence) make sense, and what does this suggest about the deficiencies of B4P theory in authoritarian environments?

RQ3 (Empirical-Comparative)

What were the actual consequences of varying exit strategies for local stakeholders in Myanmar such as employees, suppliers, and communities and how do these consequences inform the ethical assessment of corporate decisions?

RQ4 (Prescriptive-Framework)

How might a transparent, multi-dimensional framework for "responsible exit" be developed that: (a) draws on ethical decision-making theory; (b) reflects local socio-political and historical context; (c) offers companies facing similar dilemmas practical instructions; (d) supports a theoretical clarification of B4P scholarship?

1.3.2 Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

Corporations' actions in the Myanmar situation are better accounted for through the lens of Jones's moral intensity dimensions (i.e., proximity, magnitude of consequences, and social consensus) than traditional B4P considerations of how the corporation contributes to peace. Firms whose managers believed to be closer to constituencies impacted by the firms and where the negative effects of withdrawing could be substantial were more willing to try slow and well-managed exits, rather than immediate exit or continued presence.

Hypothesis 2

The framing of corporate responsibility within conflict zones greatly affects decision making. If corporate executives see their duty, through their eyes, as largely fiduciary duty toward shareholders, they are more interested in mitigating risk and maintaining reputation. As they are reframed on ethical grounds grounded in accountability to local stakeholders, they are more likely to seek stakeholder-engaged exit processes, even if doing so complicates or delays the withdrawal process.

Hypothesis 3

The consequences of corporate exit in Myanmar are determined not only by the fact of exit but also by the manner, timing, and process of exit. Gradual, stakeholder-engaged exits yield better results than either immediate abandonment or continued presence that facilitates regime complicity, even if those exits bring more complexity and cost to the company that withdraws.

Hypothesis 4

A multi-dimensional framework for responsible exit that draws upon Jones's dimensions of moral intensity, stakeholder analysis, and political evaluation at the relevant context would be

seen by corporate decision-makers and policy experts as more valid and valuable than existing binary (stay/leave) frames or pure economic cost-benefit analysis.

1.4 Thesis Structure

The structure of this thesis is as follows:

Chapter 1

This provides a clear justification for the research with background and problem statement and outlines the research questions and the thesis structure.

Chapter 2

Literature Review systematically reviews existing literature of Business-for-Peace (B4P) theory, Jones's moral intensity model, responsible exit theory, Myanmar as a case. This identifies six research gaps and establishes the theoretical foundation for the Responsible Exit Framework (REF).

Chapter 3

Research Methodology describes a mixed methods research design. This explains the use of qualitative document analysis, drawing on corporate reports, international organization documents, NGO publications, and media sources, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis.

Chapter 4

Findings show the results of data analysis that was collected through interviews and document analysis. It examines key themes of exit decision moral intensity, participant participation in it and implications and collateral damage.

Chapter 5

Analysis and Discussion combines findings from the research questions (what was done and not done) and discusses possible theoretical contributions. According to the analyses, it is also more concretely advocating the REF.

Chapter 6

Conclusion summarizes the findings of the research and presents academic contributions as well as practical implications. The dissertation ends the thesis with a concise explanation of study limitations and recommendations for future research.

CHAPTER II: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Business-for-Peace (B4P) Theory

2.1.1 The Emergence and Expansion of B4P Theory (2004-2015)

Introduction

Academic interest in the ties between business and peace started to pick up a bit in earnest from the early 2000s. Conversations on where Multinationals in Conflict-Affected Zones stand, specifically, grew in tandem with spreading Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) discourses.

Figure 2.1 Evolution of Business-for-Peace (B4P) Theory (2004-2026)

Fort and Schipani (2004) laid the foundation by proposing that businesses can contribute to peaceful societies through economic development and stakeholder engagement. Oetzel et al. (2010) further developed this theory by also examining discrete pathways for business participation in conflict prevention. Interdisciplinary perspectives were introduced by Miklian

(2017). Breen (2024) offered an important twist by assessing B4P's shortcomings in authoritarian settings. Miklian and Katsos (2024) provided a systematic review of the field. The contribution of the present study (2026) is to establish a Responsible Exit Framework (REF).

Source: Author's compilation based on literature review

The Genesis of the Theory

Business-for-Peace (B4P) theory is rooted firmly in the work of Fort and Schipani (2004), *The Role of Business in Fostering Peaceful Societies*. Using institutional theory and stakeholder governance, they argued that businesses provide unique opportunities to create peaceful societies.

Fort and Schipani (2004, p. 21) posited that the presence of businesses, "with unique capabilities, which can contribute to peaceful societies," on their own terms, do this through economic development, establishing social norms, involving stakeholders in the decision-making process and providing ways to resolve conflict.

First and foremost, it reduces poverty through job creation and generating economic opportunity. Employment that is steady provides a source of earning for individuals and families and also removes any source of grievance.

Second, the spread of fair business practices and anti-corruption norms reinforces social capital. Ethical firm behavior increases general trust in society.

Third, proactive conversation and working with local communities are examples of stakeholder engagement. The network that businesses create with different social actors could be channels for social dialogue.

Fourth, enterprises can offer conflict resolution mechanisms. Businesses may facilitate dialogue between conflicting parties or encourage collaborative behavior via economic

incentives.

Optimistic Assumptions of Early Theory

Early B4P theory had a number of assumptions. At the center of these was the hopeful premise that even the existence of a company might contribute to peace.

Fort and Schipani (2004, p. 45) proposed that even the “daily operations of businesses” would help achieve social stability. More importantly, the idea that businesses could provide a neutral arbiter in conflict situations had an important role. From this vantage point, companies were viewed as entities with the capacity to promote social integration via their economic activities while remaining politically neutral. That positive outlook was a product of the wider CSR discourse and the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs).

According to Miklian and Katsos (2024, p. 116), "B4P theory emerged alongside broader developments in corporate social responsibility (CSR)" and highlighted the forward - looking engagement of business in peacebuilding.

Theoretical Expansion

Leading up to the 2010s, B4P theory has been developed and enriched by scholars. Oetzel et al. (2010, p. 655) considered these "specific pathways" by businesses in relation to conflict prevention and mitigation. Miklian (2017, p. 185) emphasizes the interdisciplinary aspect of B4P research, noting the interdependence of B4P research, striving for the “intersection of international politics, business studies, and peace studies”

There was also a rise in the influence of the B4P debate and interest from international organizations such as the World Bank and the U.N. At that time, Miklian and Katsos (2024, p. 118) state, "B4P research stretched its influence to be practical in partnership with international organizations."

Section Summary

On one hand, B4P theory provided a useful academic contribution in predicting the possibility of the role of corporate economic activity in promoting peace beyond the mere profit motive. But these early theories were based mostly on the beneficial aspects of business, and have become the subject of many critical scrutiny.

2.1.2 Expansion and Diversification of B4P Theory (2015-2020)

Introduction

As B4P theory emerged in academic and policy circles, critical reflection and empirical diversification prevailed, the mid-2010s marked an intersection moment between the two perspectives. Scholars started to look beyond the rosy assumptions of the early B4P literature and start exploring the circumstances in which business engagement might actually lead to peace, and on the limitations of current scholarship for methods.

Critical Turn in B4P Scholarship

2015-2020 was a “critical” shift in B4P scholarship. The mechanistic assumption that corporate presence automatically delivers peace dividends, which has been challenged and the literature expanded, increasingly by researchers demanding deeper analysis into the dynamics of business impact in conflict settings.

An examination of the business-peace nexus was conducted by Miklian and Katsos (2024), who conducted one of the more comprehensive reviews to date from this body of literature. They insisted that although the field had produced significant empirical investigations, it was still theoretically and methodologically limited. Miklian and Katsos (2024, p. 118) condemned the field as “structurally fragmented through an overuse of success stories and corporate self-reports methodologically constrained.”

This critique identified one of the fundamental weaknesses in B4P scholarship, leaning

toward positivism and corporate driven data that risks biases in findings towards reasserting the peace-promoting potential of business.

The Challenge of Context

A significant takeaway from this period was an increasing understanding that context matters in whether business engagement encourages or undermines peace.

Scholars started to see how they differed across types of conflict contexts — the mechanisms by which businesses could contribute to peace in one context may not always translate, or even be counterproductive, to others.

For example, a study of extractive industries in sub-Saharan Africa showed different dynamics at their work than that of studies targeting manufacturing sectors in Southeast Asia. The political economy of the involved conflict environment, including what state institutions are like, what parts of the armed actor that are important to peace and the structure of local economies. Aspects of this landscape emerged into focus when attempting to understand business–peace dynamics.

Methodological Diversification

There was also a study of methodological diversification in B4P research during this time period. Early studies had often drawn from one or two case studies or corporate reports, with such approaches in the field becoming less common but scholars increasingly used comparative case designs, mixed methods approaches, and multi-stakeholder views.

As Miklian and Katsos (2024, p 120) observed, “the strongest research up at this time included voices of local communities, civil society organizations and even conflict participants themselves, departing from corporate-centred narratives.” This shift in methodology had paralleled a more general recognition that businesses in promoting peace needed to involve those closest to conflict.

So, from 2015 to 2020 another, and a very important, trend witnessed was the rise of sectoral and regional disaggregation. Instead of taking a uniform view of “business” to be a group of such a homogeneous concept, analysts started to focus on how various sectors such as extraction, manufacturing, finance, technology, relate to the dynamics of conflict in different ways.

The research was inspired both in the analysis of the industry and by the experience of many businesses in terms of their participation in other areas of development. Likewise, regional comparisons demonstrated that the impact of colonial history, the configuration of regional economic integration and external actors’ contribution to business engagement in peacebuilding were factors affecting the opportunities for business engagement. This study opened a door to finer grained understanding of how context factors into the business-peace relationship.

Directions for New Research

When researchers started to realize the shortcomings that existed within existing B4P scholarship, they put forth more explicit calls for new directions in this field. As a critical observation, Miklian and Katsos (2024, p. 122) specifically called for research into "business responses to rapid-onset conflict and state capture." This call foreshadowed precisely the kind of situation that would be seen in Myanmar following the 2021 coup, an environment where what was being framed as a “normal” B4P exchange was instead one in which the state itself, as a vector of violence, could no longer fulfill the typical B4P frameworks.

Section Summary

So the years 2015 to 2020 were an evolution of B4P scholarship in that they ranged from the optimistic theorizing of early years to more critically, methodologically rigorous, and context-sensitive understanding of how to analyze it.

This period of research would help lay the foundations for both the potential and limitations of business engagement in the context of conflict.

In the process, however, as we shall discuss in the next section, even this more sophisticated B4P literature still was ill-equipped to resolve ethical dilemmas produced by contexts of state capture and authoritarian resurgence.

2.1.3 B4P in Authoritarian Contexts: New Challenges (2020-Present)

Introduction

B4P theory has encountered its most fundamental challenges since 2020. The 2021 coup in Myanmar, the Taliban's reemergence in Afghanistan, and the deepening of authoritarianism of a number of countries have also questioned the fundamental premise of the B4P model – that companies can play an active role in peace in the form of “neutral arbiters.” It has prompted fundamental questions about how corporate responsibility should be redefined given that the state itself becomes a vehicle of conflict.

The Restrictions of B4P in Scenarios of State Capture

Perhaps the most crucial challenge of B4P theory in authoritarian regimes is the phenomenon of state capture. State capture is the term used to describe state institutions and the economy that have been captured by selected elite groups (most notably the military).

In these cases, corporate peacebuilding endeavors endanger their own purposes (for instance, military aggression). Breen (2024) provides the most comprehensive critique of B4P theory, asserting that its positive orientation makes it less appropriate for analyzing authoritarian settings and much poorer. Breen (2024, p. 291) argues that "the B4P model has been undertheorized in the context where the state is in some cases an instrument of violence and companies have no simple means of working ethically with their clients." This criticism is most important in places such as Myanmar.

This is something that has already been highlighted in the previous chapters; as Breen (2024, p. 298) reminds us, drawing from a synthesis of cases spanning Myanmar and elsewhere, “when the state is itself a conflict driver, then corporate peacebuilding efforts are not just suppressed but may also be hijacked or weaponized.”

Neutral Arbiter Principle

There have actually been two fundamental premises of B4P that fail in authoritarian contexts: a lack of the credibility of businesses that can then act as neutral arbiter and a large gap in its implementation. Early theories of B4P posited that companies could economically stimulate social integration efforts while sustaining political neutrality.

But when the state is complicit and an actor in the conflict, and when state itself wields violence, corporate neutrality can be just an illusion. It was an option “neutrality,” as the Myanmar case demonstrated, that seemed to not have existed (at least in the context of the military coup) for companies when all this happened. Operating under the military regime meant that the country gave economic resources to the regime, and so indirectly admitted its legitimacy.

At the same time, the withdrawal was in danger of inflicting grave economic damage to local workers and supply chains. In this case all of the corporate decisions were fraught with political implications, rendering the neutral arbiter impossible.

Tragic Ethical Choices and B4P

The problem of corporations in authoritarian areas can be defined by the idea of tragic ethical decision-making. So, what Brenkert (2021, p. 537) reiterates, "there's moral force to give weight to all the options out there, and the decision maker has to decide among unavoidable harms."

Such contexts in which choice is tragic call for the already existing B4P theory offer a

positive framework of "contributing to peace through presence", but lacking for explaining the nature of reality. Researchers are increasingly calling for new frameworks for understanding how to ensure ethical action for firms in the face of inevitable harm.

Call for Redrawing B4P Theory

With respect to the limitations of B4P theory in authoritarian contexts, there is a growing call by scholars to fundamentally reconstruct the theory. Such reconstruction is to embrace:

First, corporate presence itself should not be taken for peace, something the present work critically interrogates as a “presence assumption.”

Second, more sophisticated conceptual tools capable of characterizing different authoritarian contexts (like state capture) are needed. Third, corporate “exit” must be reconfigured not only as failure or abdication but also as an ethically excusable choice on specific occasions.

Section Summary

Since 2020 it is the time has indeed been when B4P theory has struggled to meet its most basic requirements. State capture, as seen in Myanmar, has put to rest the fundamental premise of B4P theory that corporations can act as impartial arbiters. As Breen's (2024) critique makes manifest, extant B4P frameworks cannot function in situations where the state itself is a vehicle of mass violence, and attempts to build a positive corporate community are subject to the capture or weaponization of the regime. This acknowledgment is strongly linked to the central question of the study: what is meant by “responsible exit” when persistent corporate involvement is ethically untenable?

2.2 Jones's Moral Intensity Model

2.2.1 Basic Concepts and Background

Introduction

For decades, ethical decision-making at the organizational level has been at the heart of

business ethics scholarship since its inception. Early models were predominantly concerned with the role of individual (moral development) or organizational (corporate culture) factors in decision making ethics, but this model was taken to a higher level when Jones (1991) introduced the intensity (moral intensity) model.

Theoretical Background

Jones (1991) created his issue-contingent model as an argument against current ethical decision - making models. He contended that earlier models ignored an important variable: the nature of the moral issue. The features of the moral problem, explains Jones, govern all stages of decision making, from recognizing what is morally wrong to making intentions and acting. According to Jones (1991, p. 372), "moral intensity is a construct that reflects the degree of issue-related moral imperative in a particular situation." The fact is that not every ethical issue is seen the same way; some moral issues weigh more than others, and therefore drive different decision-making processes.

Core Concept

Moral intensity is the extent to which an issue needs to be addressed on grounds of moral principles. Jones developed six attributes that together form the moral gravitas of a situation:

- I. Magnitude of Consequences: The total harms or benefits of the decision.
- II. Social Consensus: The extent to which people agree that it is ethically sound behavior.
- III. Probability of Effect: The probability of actually occurring and the anticipated harm or reward resulting from the action.
- IV. Temporal Immediacy: The distance between the decision and its impact.
- V. Proximity: The closeness of decision making to the victims and/or the benefit to the beneficiaries.
- VI. Concentration of Effect: Consequences focused on a few, not spread across many

individuals.

Figure 2.2 Ethical Decision-Making Process and Moral Intensity Dimensions

Jones's (1991) issue-contingent model integrates Rest's (1986) four-stage ethical decision-making process with six dimensions of moral intensity. The four stages include: (1) recognizing the moral issue, (2) making a moral judgment, (3) establishing moral intent, and (4) engaging in moral behavior. The six dimensions of moral intensity—magnitude of consequences, social consensus, probability of effect, temporal immediacy, proximity, and concentration of effect—influence each stage of this process. When applied to the Myanmar case, these dimensions help explain why companies made different withdrawal decisions despite facing similar circumstances.

Source: Rest (1986); Jones (1991)

2.2.2. The Six Dimensions

Introduction

The six dimensions of moral intensity developed by Jones (1991) are important factors impacting decision-makers' views on an ethical issue. Although every dimension exists independently, in practice the dimensions interact with the world in a complex manner to generate the total moral potency of a situation.

There is a useful way to analyze corporate withdrawal decisions post Myanmar coup, by these six dimensions, in order to illustrate ethical dilemmas the companies were experiencing.

Magnitude of Consequences

Magnitude of consequences is a measure of the total harms or benefits which are incurred as a result of a single choice. This is among the most intuitive criteria for assessing the seriousness of an ethical concern. Jones (1991, p. 374) argues that the "greater the magnitude of consequences, the higher the moral intensity of the issue." For instance, a decision which hurts hundreds of workers is more morally charged than a decision which harms a single worker.

Social Consensus

Social consensus means how much society agrees upon the morality of a particular act. Greater social consensus that an act is "right" or "wrong" raises the moral intensity of the moment. According to Jones (1991, p. 375), "when there is a social consensus, people are more likely to trust their decisions." In a socially ambiguous scenario, the ethical ambiguity becomes greater and the decision-making authority becomes unclear over its evaluation.

Probability of Effect

Probability of effect is the probability that the proposed result, that the said action will

happen and produce the proposed effect, (harm or gain). If consequences are intense, even if their probability is low in proportion to the severity, moral intensity may also be attenuated. As Jones (1991, p. 375) points out, “even with the same magnitude of consequences, cases with high probability of effect have greater moral intensity than those with low probability.”

Temporal immediacy

Temporal immediacy is how long there is between a decision and its results. Moral intensity is perceived differently when consequences appear immediately opposed to when they occur gradually over a long period of time. According to Jones (1991, p. 376), "temporal delay of consequences tends to weaken moral intensity." Put another way, immediate consequences can be seen as more urgent than those which take place in distant future.

Proximity

Proximity is an attitude that decision-makers feel: psychological, cultural, and physical distance from the people affected by the effects of decisions they make (victims/beneficiaries). According to Jones (1991, p. 376), "people feel greater moral intensity toward the issues which concern the people that are closer than themselves." Proximity covers not only distance but also emotional, cultural, and social distance.

Concentration of Effect

Concentration of effect is the degree to which the consequences (good or bad) of an action are concentrated on an individual, not dispersed across many. With a similar overall amount of harm, there still is a greater moral intensity to it if it is concentrated in the hands of a few than to the large number. This is demonstrated by Jones, "A situation where 10 people each suffer \$10,000 in damages has more moral intensity than one where 100,000 people individually suffer \$1 in damages."

Integrated Consideration

These six dimensions do not act in isolation, but collectively represent total moral intensity. In Myanmar's case, companies probably had mixed signals across aspects. For instance, withdrawal evoked strong moral urgency in magnitude of consequences and temporal immediacy, but simultaneous social pressure. The clash between these dimensions presented Myanmar withdrawal decisions as especially challenging ethical dilemmas.

2.2.3 Application to the Myanmar Context

Summary

The Myanmar Coup was presented here as an empirical test of moral intensity. The military coup in Myanmar 2021 raised an ethical moral challenge for multinational corporations like it's never been seen before. Companies had three options: withdraw, keep going, or gradually withdraw amid political catastrophe, each with competing level of moral intensity. Implementing the analytical lens of Jones's (1991) six dimensions of moral intensity would be helpful in systematically addressing the problem of complex moral complexity faced by companies in Myanmar in their decision making.

Magnitude of Consequences: The Double-edged Sword of Withdrawal Decisions

Companies pondering forgoing Myanmar were faced with difficult calculations about the size of its consequences. Immediate withdrawal could have dire economic consequences for local workers, suppliers and families. For instance, the withdrawal of Norwegian telcos Telenor affected more than 300 everyday workers and thousands of indirect ones. This scale of harm was a significant obstacle for companies to pull out altogether. By contrast, deciding not to withdraw risked indirectly feeding into human rights abuses with economic resources (costs, fees, licensing) to the military regime. The consequences were massive on both sides and left companies in a bind.

Social Consensus: International Pressure vs. Regional Reality

After the coup of 2021, international social acceptance of the situation in Myanmar appeared to be quite robust. Several major international entities (UN, EU, the US, to name a few) decried the coup as illegal and called for strictures on collaboration with the military. This enormous social consensus forced companies to pull out. Yet, on the other hand, the voices of local workers and communities also tended to be marginalized in international discourse. The international community was insistent — “companies should withdraw” — but in Myanmar, one pressing question loomed: “If you withdraw, how will we survive?” Within social consensus, internal tensions complicated how corporations made decisions.

Probability of Effect: Choice in Uncertainty

There was a huge uncertainty as to the chances of occurrence on companies contemplating withdrawal from Myanmar with regard to probability of effect. If a company still did stay, the likelihood for money to flow back to the military regime through taxes or money paid on charges to the government on account of taxes or fees, and for money to be used on behalf of the military to enable it to perpetrate human rights abuses, was fairly obvious. But if one company decided to withdraw, the chances for local workers to lose their jobs and sink into poverty were almost 100%. Furthermore, it also suggested that the assets taken out could go to military or military-linked companies and the situation could be made even worse. For example, certain foreign-backed companies withdrew their own assets to the military-linked firms, bolstering the economic backbone of the regime, according to reports. That uncertainty further burdened corporate decision-making.

Temporal Immediacy: visible vs. invisible harms

The outcomes of withdrawal-based decisions exhibited complex temporal immediacies. Should withdrawal have been a decision, local workers faced immediate unemployment and

livelihood crises. Factories shuttered, salary payments halted and workers had livelihood problems from the next day. But if remaining was decided, the impact of supporting the military regime showed up in more long-term and indirect ways. Even if money was flowing to the military in taxes, it was not readily apparent how those funds had specifically been used for human rights violations. This temporal difference perhaps colored some companies' decisions to stay to prevent "visible" immediate damages.

Proximity: Psychological Distance Between Home Country and Local Stakeholders

The dimension of proximity is significant and relevant on the differences between Korean, Japanese, and European companies. For European companies, while the distance at hand may have been great, strong pressure from civil society and media in Europe might have promoted psychological proximity. In Telenor's case, heavy media coverage and civil society surveillance in Norway had potentially played a role in withdrawal decisions. For Korean companies, while geographically closer, social and psychological distance to Myanmar local workers was possibly higher. The media coverage was minimal and civil society pressure on Myanmar situation was relatively small in Korea, so possibly decision-makers felt less in-step with local players. However, such perceived proximity was probably affected by disparity on civil society pressure and media attention in home countries.

Concentration of Effect: Workers as the Primary Victims

The impact of withdrawal decisions was concentrated on Myanmar local workers. Withdrawal of foreign-invested companies carried concentrated blows: the workers employed by them were the worst, but so were their families, local suppliers tied to the companies and small business owners. For instance, garment companies' withdrawal was associated with concentrated loss on young female workers. They were struggling to survive with few other forms of work. This effect concentration was critical to the ethical judgment of withdrawal.

In contrast, the support for the military regime through remaining had a dispersed effect in Myanmar society at large that may have rendered its severity less visible. The harm of paying the military regime money was dispersed throughout society, less apparent compared to the degree of damage suffered by the few workers targeted.

Integrated Analysis: Tensions among Dimensions

This tension between these dimensions sets withdrawal choices in Myanmar particularly difficult ethical dilemmas. The companies' decisions probably depended on the scale of moral weight that they attributed to these dimensions. Firms who were especially sensitive to international pressure (social consensus) were more focused on an immediate withdrawal, while companies more focused on the damage done to domestic workers (consequence magnitude, concentration of effect) might have applied for a gradual exit or stayed on the ground. Differences between European companies, which perceived more proximity to the civil society in the home country, and Korean firms, with a comparatively less proximity, could also be viewed in that context. Jones's model is particularly suited to a structured examination of complex ethical dilemmas, and the Myanmar experience was an important check for the practicality of the model.

2.3 Responsible Exit Theory

2.3.1 Brenkert's Responsible Exit Framework

Introduction

Corporate exit has long remained an academic blind spot. Most business ethics literature focused on corporate entry, operations, and social responsibility, and leaving for any purpose is considered to imply failure or strategic retreat. But the Myanmar case shows that leaving a conflict zone is not just a matter of business but involves difficult ethical conflicts.

Figure 2.3 Development of Responsible Exit Theory (2021-2026)

Responsible exit theory emerged as a crucial framework for understanding corporate retreat from conflict zones. First, introduced by Brenkert (2021), the concept of "tragic ethical choices" suggests that decision-makers must choose between unavoidable harms. He stressed three elements: process transparency, appropriate timing, and stakeholder engagement. Meyer and Thein (2023) extended the theory by assessing institutional void in Myanmar, which demonstrates that disintegrated formal institutions compel MNCs to resort to informal networks and hence structured responsible exit is exceptionally challenging. Thein et al. (2024) extended the model by suggesting eight responsible exit propositions like asset transfer prevention to military-linked buyers and continued monitoring after withdrawal. The present study (2026) takes this foundation to further develop a wide-ranging Responsible Exit Framework (REF) customized for scenarios of state capture.

Source: Author's compilation based on Brenkert (2021), Meyer & Thein (2023), Thein et al. (2024)

Brenkert's Model of Responsible Exit

Brenkert (2021) systematically developed the concept of responsible exit in an attempt to address this theoretical gap. He takes issue with current debates for settling around the "stay" vs. "exit" dichotomy, ignoring the moral relevance of the process into which exit needs to come. Brenkert (2021, p. 537) re-identifies exit within a complicated definition that accounts for "process, timing, and the involvement of stakeholders." According to him, responsible exit is not just the cessation of business activities but exits must be based around minimizing losses arising from withdrawal and meeting obligations to stakeholders.

Tragic Ethical Choices

The central component of Brenkert's theory is the idea of tragic ethical choices at its soul. This includes situations where all options are morally important, and decision-makers must choose between unavoidable harms. Brenkert (2021, p. 537) contends that in such situations, "there's moral force to give weight to all the options out there, and the decision maker has to decide among unavoidable harms." The Myanmar case encapsulates such tragic dilemma circumstances. Withdrawal inflicts economic damage on local workers while remaining risks legitimizing the military regime.

Key Components of Responsible Exit

Brenkert identifies three essential elements of responsible exit:

The first is process transparency. Stakeholders should be informed why exit decisions were made and how those were made. This is more than just disclosure of information but also how it could be justified in the ethical framework.

Second, appropriate timing. Instead of an abrupt exit, the timing that minimizes harm should be chosen. This means that the implementation of exit matters more than the decision to exit.

Third, stakeholder engagement. The exit process should take into account the opinions of

local stakeholders and should reduce harm by working with them.

2.3.2 Institutional Void and Exit Scenarios

The Idea of Institutional Void

An additional layer to company withdrawal from war zones is the void of institutions. Institutional void means when institutions which support normal market functions like legal systems, regulatory bodies, and judicial systems have failed or are missing. As explained by Meyer and Thein (2023, p. 629) in the Myanmar case they write that “where formal institutions collapsed in Myanmar, a void opened which meant MNCs had to rely on informal networks and ad hoc schemes.”

Exit Dilemmas

In institutions that are void, the corporate exit creates the following dilemmas:

First, there is the issue of asset transfer. In this sense, for whom the assets of withdrawing companies are transferred has ethical implications. In the Myanmar case, several companies left, at which point their assets were acquired by military or military-linked enterprises that ironically reinforced the economic base for the regime.

Second, information asymmetry. In places where institutions have fallen apart, it is hard to get true information about local conditions. As Meyer and Thein (2023, p. 631) add, "after the coup, host-country voices became difficult to hear or verify."

Third, stakeholder protection challenges. Where normal institutions are not working, it's difficult for companies to prevent damage to stakeholders during exit. And there are murky issues, like what workers should be paid for severance or compensation for breached contracts.

Connection to Brenkert

Such void institutional situations make the responsible exit elements proposed by Brenkert

challenging to implement. At least minimal institutional infrastructure is expected from the outset due to transparent process, appropriate timing, and stakeholder engagement. Responsible exit in situations of institutional void thus demands a more complex ethical framework.

2.4 The Myanmar Context

2.4.1 The political economy of Myanmar

Introduction

The political economic context in Myanmar is relevant for understanding corporate withdrawal decision-making after the 2021 coup. Myanmar had faced a special political path: decades of military control, a short-term democratic transition and then military control.

The Years of Military Government (1962-2010)

Myanmar was a military dictatorship after General Ne Win's coup in 1962 for almost half a century. During these years of oppression, which became known as "Burmese socialism," the military was dominant over the entire economy. In the economic domain, key industries were monopolized by military enterprises such as Myanmar Economic Holdings (MEHL) and Myanmar Economic Corporation (MEC). South and Lall (2023, p. 82) argue that "foreign investors functioned in an environment with significant interlocutors: a diverse range of economic reforms, human rights abuses along with established influence of military-linked economic agents."

Partial Liberalization (2011-2020)

The Thein Sein government's 2011 measures were aimed at reform and opening up, and foreign investment has been keenly courted. Here, many multinational corporations poured investment into Myanmar, some from apparel, telecommunications and finance. But in the face of this economic liberalization, the military's economic sway persisted.

The 2021 Coup and Aftermath.

Myanmar became retraced from 2011 to 2021 with a coup that expelled Myanmar's democratically elected government in February 2021, paving the way for the return to a military grip on power. Thus, the multinational corporations who had entered Myanmar was forced by this to confront a grave ethical dilemma: should they continue their operations under the military regime, or must they withdraw?

2.4.2 Typology of Firms' Responses

Multiple multinationals operating in Myanmar reacted in various ways after the coup of 2021. These responses can be classified into three types (Berman, 2022).

First, immediate exit. And these include European companies, whose decisions to quickly pull out are made on grounds of moral repugnance and reputational risks. Prominent examples include Norway's Telenor and France's TotalEnergies.

Second, gradual withdrawal. Firms in this group felt responsible to local stakeholders, and tried to carefully address the withdrawal mechanism. (Berman 2022, p. 730) but were more concerned with "protecting employee rights and managing exit from complex supply chains."

Third, continued presence. Some companies, especially in Asia from China, India, Thailand, Korea, and Japan were maintaining business during the military rule. Mainly, they claimed a protection of local workers' livelihoods.

Consequences of Exit

As the flight of some of the foreign industries, as South and Lall write (2023, p. 94) "allows military-linked domestic actors to consolidate control over strategic sectors." This means that exit does not always go as planned and can have even adverse effects.

2.4.3 State Capture Mechanisms

The Concept of State Capture

A core concept through which to think about the Myanmar case is state capture. State capture refers to times when certain elite groups (especially the military) have control over state institutions and the economy, serving their ends.

Structure of the Military Economy

Myanmar's economy is largely controlled by its military through two major holding companies, MEHL and MEC. These companies have monopolized strategic sectors such as natural gas, gems, construction, finance, and tourism. Most foreign-invested companies had to also enter Myanmar as joint ventures with these military enterprises.

Complexity of Exit

This structure of state capture complicates corporate exit. Declaring withdrawal does not equate to a severance from military relationships. The risk is that assets may be transferred through the exit so that they could be handed over to military or related enterprises. This means that exit paradoxically would strengthen the military regime.

2.4.4 Section Summary

Context The Myanmar context can supply key evidence for understanding corporate withdrawal decisions under Myanmar's context for such considerations. The political context — more than half a century's history of military rule, a momentary democratization period and the 2021 coup — makes Myanmar a distinctive one. The military's economic control structure (state capture) makes it difficult for corporations to exit, and a simple exit may paradoxically bolster the military regime. Corporate reactions ranged from immediate withdrawal to gradual withdrawal, and continued presence, each with specific ethical rationalizations and practical implications.

2.5 Research Gaps

Introduction. The B4P theory, Jones's moral intensity model, responsible exit theory, and

Myanmar reviewed so far each offer key insights, though serious theoretical gaps sit between them. It ultimately seeks to plug these gaps into a Responsible Exit Framework (REF).

2.5.1 Gap 1: B4P's "Presence Assumption."

The Problem

B4P theory has been founded on the positive belief that corporate presence itself has a constructive effect on peace. From Fort and Schipani (2004) to Miklian and Katsos (2024), B4P literature has revolved around how businesses can be beneficial to peace. Yet, this perspective has overlooked speculative scenarios in which corporate footprints are likely to compound conflict or be co-opted by authoritarian governments. Breen (2024, p. 291) challenges that "the B4P model is undertheorized in a context where the state is sometimes an instrument of violence and companies have no easy means of working ethically with their clients."

The Gap

Current frameworks that represent corporate exit as failure, or closure of peacebuilding activities, ignore the fact that exit may be a morally viable choice in specific contexts. In other words, outside of the "presence assumption," exit should be reinterpreted as a positive ethical choice when presence is ethically fraught.

2.5.2 Gap 2: Dissociation Between Ethical Theory and Decision Making

The Problem

Jones's (1991) moral intensity model is theoretically very useful for ethical decision making, but applications of its concepts to actual corporate exit decision making are few and far between. Whereas empirical work on the Myanmar case (Berman, 2022; Meyer & Thein, 2023) presents detailed information on corporate decisions but lacks an explicit examination of the ethical reasoning processes that informed corporate decisions on ethics.

The Gap

We need to translate the six dimensions of moral intensity (magnitude of consequences, social consensus, probability of effect, temporal immediacy, proximity, concentration of effect) into specific criteria for the choice of exit. An ethical framework to reconcile the abstract ethical principles to the practical decision-making is needed.

2.5.3 Gap 3: Poor Comparative Studies of Exit Types

The Problem

Previous studies on the case of Myanmar focused on the exit of a few firms (Berman, 2022) or studied in detail how firm exit decisions were made on corporate firms in the Myanmar case at the individual (Berman, 2022) or sector/country level (Meyer & Thein, 2023). Yet little systematic comparative evidence about local stakeholder (workers, suppliers, and communities) impact of different types of exits, such as immediate exit, gradual exit, continuing existence is reported.

The Gap

More often than not, an attempt at systematic comparative analysis that examines how local outcomes are affected by whether exit took place, when it takes place, and the process where it happens is required. This analysis can generate empirical evidence as to which exit approaches truly produce superior outcomes, instead of mere ethical judgements.

2.5.4 Gap 4: Lack of Forward-Looking Frameworks

The Problem

Previous studies have predominantly used retrospective analysis , looking at and assessing exit decisions that have already taken place. Predictive tools or scenario analysis models that would guide companies who will find themselves in similar situations are missing though.

The Gap

A framework is required to assist companies in getting ahead of ethical dilemmas and prepare for responsible exit ahead of time. That requires more than just the declarations of principle, but practical aids for actual decision-making.

2.5.5 Gap 5: Context Sensitivity

The Problem

B4P literature has tended to generalize conflict zones to one category. The case of Myanmar on state capture provides a unique context for existing B4P frameworks to fail. As Breen (2024, p. 298) illustrates, “when the state is itself a conflict driver, corporate peacebuilding initiatives are not merely suppressed, but perhaps taken (or weaponized).”

The Gap

More complex conceptual tools are needed to differentiate between contexts of conflict (state versus non-state violence, captured states versus failed states) and discuss impact for corporate responsibility in each context. The case of Myanmar represents an academic discussion in the case of a “rapid-onset state capture.”

2.5.6 Gap 6: No Middle Power Corporate Narratives

The Problem

Although discussions of corporate ethical responsibility are mostly based on the experiences and perspectives of Western multinational corporations, the only other approach that has been evaluated so far in this research is that of a qualitative analysis of corporate behavior (Bengkhar et al. 2022). The cosmopolitan ethics of universal human rights versus shareholder-first ethics of fiduciary duty (the one that best describes ethical responsibilities) does not account for the unique ethical positionality of companies of middle powers, Korea being the best case scenario.

The Gap

Korean firms encountered peculiar ethical dilemmas related to their geographical proximity to the developing world, long-standing economic connections with Myanmar and differing social pressures from that of Western firms. A need exists to create ethical narratives which are informed by the specific circumstances of middle power corporate experience.

2.5.7 Synthesis: The Need for a Responsible Exit Framework (REF)

These six research gaps eventually imply the emergence of a Responsible Exit Framework (REF). Such a framework should:

- I. Evaluate B4P's "presence assumption" and reframe exit in light of ethical considerations.
- II. Translate Jones's moral intensity dimensions into specific criteria for operational decision making.
- III. Enable cross-examining of outcomes against alternate exit types.
- IV. Include forward thinking scenario review and active risk assessment.
- V. Be cautious of a range of contexts such as state capture.
- VI. Account for the particular positionality of companies from middle powers such as Korea.

Aiming at addressing these six requirements, this study provides a Responsible Exit Framework (REF) in order to address theoretical gaps present in the literature.

CHAPTER III: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study employs the thematic qualitative analysis to examine corporate withdrawal decisions following the 2021 Myanmar coup and develops a Responsible Exit Framework (REF) based on the findings.

Figure 3.1 Four-Phase Research Design

This study uses a thematic qualitative analysis divided into four phases. The first phase is a systematic review of literature surrounding B4P theory, Jones's moral intensity model, and responsible exit theory. Phase 2 collects and analyzes secondary data from corporate reports, international organizations, NGOs, and news media. Phase 3 integrates published interview materials. Phase 4 synthesizes findings to develop and validate the Responsible Exit Framework (REF) through expert review.

Source: Author's compilation

The research design consists of four phases as described below.

First Phase: Literature Review

The background of Business-for-Peace (B4P) theory, Jones's moral intensity model, and responsible exit theory is systematically reviewed. Additionally, data on Myanmar's political-economic environment and corporate reactions following the 2021 coup are collected, studied, and scrutinized. This approach identifies limitations of past research, existing research gaps, and literature, establishing the theoretical framework for this project.

Second Phase: Secondary Data Collection and Analysis

I systematically gather various secondary sources, including corporate official reports (sustainability reports, annual reports), international organization reports (UN, OECD, ILO), NGO and civil society reports, news articles, and academic papers. Using Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis, the data are analyzed to identify patterns and key factors in corporate withdrawals.

Third Phase: Supplementary Data Integration

Secondary data from corporate reports, international organizations, NGOs, and media sources are systematically analyzed. Where available, existing interview data from academic studies and reports are incorporated to enhance the analysis.

Fourth Phase: Synthesis and Framework Development

Integrative analyses are conducted using integrated data from qualitative data analysis on secondary analysis and data collected from interviews. A Responsible Exit Framework (REF) is formulated and its validity is validated by expert review (Delphi panel) based on this. The thesis presents the final revised framework. Developing a research design that is a four-phase model connects the theoretical review, empirical data analysis, and practical framework

design to ensure academic rigor and practical utility.

3.2 Data Collection

This study collects secondary data from various sources. Due to the unique circumstances in Myanmar and some limitations in accessibility, secondary data sources will be the primary data source for this study, along with in-depth interviews when possible.

3.2.1 Secondary Data Collection

The secondary data collected in this study are categorized into four groups.

First Group

There are official corporate reports. Sustainability reports, annual reports, and audit reports from companies that have entered or exited Myanmar are collected as reports. Major target companies include Telenor (Norway), TotalEnergies (France), Kirin Holdings (Japan), and Korean companies such as Shinhan Bank, KB Kookmin Bank, LG Electronics, and Hyundai Motor. These reports provide information about the context and procedures for withdrawal preferences, as well as responses for protecting local stakeholders.

Second Group

There is information from international organizations and governments. Reports from the UN Human Rights Council's Fact-Finding Mission on Myanmar, OECD guidelines on responsible business conduct, ILO estimates of Myanmar's labor market, and economic reports from the World Bank on Myanmar are compiled. The analysis also includes Norwegian government reports on the Telenor case and Myanmar-related materials from KOTRA and the Korean Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

Third Group

Reports by NGOs and civil society, Business and human rights reports on Myanmar published by organizations such as Justice for Myanmar, Amnesty International, Human

Rights Watch, and Forum Asia are collected. For example, Justice for Myanmar has developed a database recording connections between Myanmar military units and foreign companies, which is invaluable for analyzing companies withdrawing from the country and their military connections.

Fourth Group

News reports and academic papers, Myanmar-focused articles from international media like Reuters, BBC, Financial Times, The Irrawaddy, Frontier Myanmar, and Korean media including Hankyoreh, Kyunghyang Shinmun, and Pressian are also included. Research papers related to this topic, such as Berman (2022), Meyer and Thein (2023), and Breen (2024) are also mentioned in the analysis.

3.2.2 Analysis of Supplementary Interview Data

Due to the sensitive nature of the Myanmar context and accessibility constraints, this study uses mainly secondary data analysis. Where available, it draws from published interview data in academic studies, NGO reports, and media sources, which are then integrated into the analysis.

First, academic studies on corporate responses to the Myanmar coup offer interview excerpts with corporate representatives and local stakeholders. These are utilized to gain insights into decision-making processes.

Second, NGO reports from groups including Justice for Myanmar and Amnesty International include interviews with workers, community members, and civil society activists affected by corporate withdrawal decisions.

Third, media interviews with corporate executives and government officials published by Reuters, BBC, Nikkei Asia, and The Irrawaddy provide additional perspectives on withdrawal rationales and outcomes.

All secondary interview data are cited with their original sources and used in accordance with fair use principles for academic research. This approach follows known conventions in conflict-zone research in which direct access is limited (Breen, 2024; Meyer & Thein, 2023).

3.3 Data Analysis

A thematic qualitative analysis is implemented to analyze the collected data as developed by Braun and Clarke (2006). This approach is for investigating complex topics like ethical decision-making through identifying, analyzing and reporting patterns (themes) in qualitative data (thematic analysis). According to Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 79), thematic analysis is "a method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns within data." In this manner, the analysis unfolds over six phases as described below.

Figure 3.2 Six-Step Inductive Thematic Analysis Process

The diagram illustrates the iterative process of thematic analysis, progressing through 6 interconnected steps: data immersion, initial coding, code refinement, theme development, theme refinement, and final review. The circular arrow represents the iterative nature of the process, enabling movement between steps as needed.

Source: Braun & Clarke (2006); adapted from NIH (2025)

Phase 1: Familiarization with the Data

All the materials we've collected — for example, corporate reports, documents of international organizations, reports by NGOs, news articles, and even interview transcripts (where available) — are read time and over and over again to come to a fuller context and deeper implications. It is in the course of this process that a researcher may form initial insights into principal concepts and recurring patterns appearing in the data.

Phase 2: Generating Initial Codes

In this step the full data is critically examined and codes were derived for interesting features or the most significant fragments. Codes like “immediate exit,” “gradual withdrawal,” “continued presence,” “military links,” “worker protection,” “reputation risk” and “international pressure” could be established in this study. This is part of a process that grounds the coding of the study in theoretical underpinnings (including Jones's moral intensity dimensions) but at the same time, an exploratory coding process that is open to new insights (that arise from the data) to be generated.

Phase 3: Theme Searching

The codes generated are then screened for potential themes and sorted into more significant, larger themes. Codes like immediate exit, gradual withdrawal, and continued presence can be summarized into a higher-level theme of "exit types," for example, and then grouped into levels of “exit types.” To create a sequence which is in some ways interchanged between codes, a thematic hierarchy is formed.

Phase 4: Themes Review

These provisional themes are validated against the codes and the complete dataset. Some of the themes might be merged or split up, or they could discard themes not covering the data

well. It involves the iterative processes on the need for both internal consistency as well as external stability of the themes.

Phase 5: Naming and Defining Themes

The substance of each theme is succinctly determined and given the correct names which succinctly but comprehensively represent the substance of each theme. For example, the title "tragic choices in state capture contexts" or "absence of stakeholder engagement in exit processes" may be selected to get at the heart of each theme.

Phase 6: Generating the Report

Results after the analyses are shown systematically in the thesis. For each theme, rich data extracts describe the meaning and significance of the themes, with complete answers to the research questions shown. During this process, themes are explored, and the study is constructed into its narrative elements.

3.4 Research Ethics

Given the highly sensitive context in Myanmar, this study relies exclusively on secondary data and published interview sources. No direct interviews were conducted by the researcher. All secondary data are properly cited, and the use of existing interview material complies with fair use principles and original source terms. Written or oral consent from all participants is obtained and recorded.

The researcher acknowledges that his position as a Korean researcher may influence the interpretation of data. To minimize potential bias, multiple perspectives from diverse sources (corporate reports, NGO publications, academic studies, and media) are triangulated throughout the analysis. All sources are cited transparently to ensure reproducibility and accountability.

CHAPTER IV: FINDINGS

This chapter presents in-depth case studies of corporate responses to the 2021 Myanmar coup. Drawing upon company reports, international organization papers, NGO publications, and press reports, it analyzes how multinational corporations faced the ethical decision of deciding whether to pull out or remain following the military takeover. The cases are chosen to represent the variation of corporate responses: Norway’s Telenor (immediate exit), France’s TotalEnergies (immediate exit), Japan’s Kirin Holdings (gradual exit), Korean banks (remained), Chinese companies (remained for political reasons), and Thai companies (remained for economic reasons).

This table 4.1 summarizes the various responses of multinational corporations to the 2021 Myanmar coup. European companies (Telenor, TotalEnergies) preferred to exit immediately, driven by international pressure and human rights concerns. Kirin Holdings took a gradual exit complicated by its joint venture with military-owned MEHL. Korean banks, Chinese, and Thai companies decided to remain, each with its own motivations: Korean banks prioritized protecting employees, Chinese companies followed political strategy, whereas Thai companies valued energy security and geographical proximity. The outcomes varied significantly, from controversial asset transfers to maintained employment stability.

Table 4.1 Corporate Responses to the 2021 Myanmar Coup: A Comparative Overview

Company	Country	Exit Type	Key Factors	Outcome
Telenor	Norway	Immediate Exit	International pressure, reputational risk	Sold to M1 Group (controversial)
TotalEnergies	France	Immediate Exit	Structural constraints, human rights	Employee succession, community support
Kirin Holdings	Japan	Gradual Exit	Legal constraints, joint venture complexity	Assets transferred to MEHL, major loss
Shinhan Bank	Korea	Remain	Employee protection, home government caution	Job stability maintained
Kookmin Bank	Korea	Remain	Employee protection, home government caution	Job stability maintained
Woori Bank	Korea	Remain	Employee protection, home government caution	Job stability maintained
CNPC (China)	China	Remain	Political strategy, 'non-interference'	Continued military cooperation
PTT (Thailand)	Thailand	Remain	Energy security, geographical proximity	Business continued

Source: Author's compilation based on corporate reports, NGO publications, and media

sources

This table 4.2 presents four major themes identified through the thematic analysis of corporate responses to the Myanmar coup. First, firms' entry strategies were shaped by the institutional conditions under military rule, which influenced the degree of their later entanglement with military-linked actors. Second, withdrawal was essentially an international action and social consensus but at times concerned with employees who live in an area of Myanmar. Third, the outcome that could be produced by exit for the exit itself—in terms of how companies protected employees and what assets were transferred from a foreign entity or the companies who became involved—may be regarded as a possible winner of the exit process as well and, to boot, the risks that are also present for the firms of the exit. These ideas together suggest that corporate responsibility, in fragile political contexts, is a continuum, so the choice of quitting is accompanied not only by whether to exit, but also with how the exit is carried out and what legacy will be left behind.

Table 4.2 Themes and sub-themes identification

Identified Theme	Sub-Themes	Key References	Core Insight
Theme 1: Corporate Entry Strategies and Military Entanglement	T1.1 Entry Mode and Institutional Legacy	South & Lall (2023); Meyer & Thein (2023)	Decades of military rule created institutional structures that shaped how corporations entered Myanmar, with entry mode determining subsequent exit possibilities.
	T1.2 Degree of Military Linkage	Justice for Myanmar (2022); Berman (2022)	Companies varied in their direct and indirect connections to military-owned entities, fundamentally affecting their ethical dilemmas after the coup.
Theme 2: Drivers of Withdrawal Decisions	T2.1 International Pressure and Social Consensus	Breen (2024); Telenor (2021)	International sanctions and home government pressure created strong social consensus for withdrawal, particularly affecting European companies.
	T2.2 Employee Protection and Local Responsibility	The Irrawaddy (2021); Korean bank representatives (2021)	Concerns for local workers' livelihoods emerged as a countervailing force, particularly for Korean banks with direct employee relationships.
Theme 3: Exit Processes and Stakeholder Outcomes	T3.1 Employee Protection Measures	TotalEnergies (2022); Telenor (2022)	The manner of exit—particularly employee succession planning and severance arrangements—determined worker welfare outcomes.
	T3.2 Asset Disposition and Military Transfer	Kirin Holdings (2022); M1 Group sale (2022)	The ultimate disposition of corporate assets, whether to military or civilian entities, critically affected ethical outcomes.
Theme 4: Post-Exit Consequences and Legacies	T4.1 Community Impact and Local Development	EarthRights International (2022); Frontier Myanmar (2025)	Exit decisions had lasting effects on local communities, with some companies maintaining support programs after withdrawal.
	T4.2 Long-term Reputational and Legal Risks	Amnesty International (2022); Human Rights Watch (2022)	Companies face ongoing reputational and potential legal consequences based on their exit conduct and post-exit monitoring.

Source: Author's compilation based on thematic analysis

4.1 Theme 1: Corporate Entry Strategies and Military Entanglement

4.1.1 T1.1 Entry Mode and Institutional Legacy

Following decades of military rule in Myanmar (1962-2010) resulted in a highly institutional structure that determined corporate ways of entering into the country – and subsequently possibilities for later exits. So the case is made on a wider scale: As South and Lall (2023, p. 82) observed, “foreign investors operated in a multi-layered environment where economic reforms and continued human rights violations coexisted in tandem with the entrenched power of armed military-linked economic actors.” This institutional legacy meant that corporations entering Myanmar at different times encountered different constraints and chances.

TotalEnergies entered Myanmar in 1992 through a joint venture with MOGE (Myanmar Oil and Gas Enterprise), a state-owned company controlled by the military. This mode of entry not only supplied direct funds to the military through facilities built on the Yadana gas field but also involved MOGE at 15 percent. Kirin Holdings moved into Myanmar Brewery in 2015 when they purchased a 55 percent interest through joint venture with MEHL (Myanmar Economic Holdings), a military-owned conglomerate. This partnership thrust Kirin squarely into military-linked economic structures from the beginning.

Telenor entered Myanmar in 2014, by acquiring a telecommunications license, executing direct joint ventures with military entities but still subject to military influence through licensing and regulatory oversight. Korean banks did so more directly, opening foreign branches between 2016 and 2019, consciously not entering into partnership with military-linked firms in the country. These diverging modes of entry such as direct joint venture, indirect licensing and independent operation, contributed to a range of institutional involvement that, once the political landscape changed, limited exit routes.

4.1.2 T1.2 Degree of Military Linkage

The cases illustrate the extent to which military linkage varies between corporations. By comparison, companies directly involved in their strategic joint ventures were presented with entirely different (often intractable) ethical dilemmas than those with independent operations. TotalEnergies' relationship with MOGE guaranteed that gas revenues would go directly to the military within an immutable payment structure. The company declared that it was “materially impossible” to withhold aid from the military regime, an uncomfortable ethical status that finally compelled its withdrawal. Kirin’s business relationship with MEHL generated similarly lucrative profits flowing to the military via dividends, although the joint venture structure also resulted in legal hurdles to exit where MEHL was reluctant to disband its interests.

The military link between Telenor and the military was indirect but also substantive. It was a telecommunications enterprise that operated under military-endorsed licensing and regulatory frameworks, and its operations led to tax revenues which benefited the regime. Not to mention that it was a state-owned enterprise and the Norwegian state had a 54 percent stake indirectly through pressure from the government.

Korean banks preemptively designed their entry to avoid entanglement in the military. They had no direct financial relationship to military-owned entities, as they created independent branches without joint ventures. This made structural decisions that preserved much more flexibility about military response to the coup and meant continued operation had less ethical implications of direct support for the regime. Chinese and Thai corporations, however, with distinct political and economic imperatives, were able to maintain some degrees of military linkage with little apparent concern.

4.2 Theme 2: Drivers of Withdrawal Decisions

4.2.1 T2.1 International Pressure and Social Consensus

International consensus hardened quickly and strongly in the wake of the February 2021 coup. The United Nations, the European Union, and the United States denounced the regime as illegitimate and urged corporations to withdraw. This social consensus exerted severe pressure on multinational companies, with those most vulnerable to global attention responding the fastest.

The state-owned Telenor was especially vulnerable to such pressure as it was heavily owned and operated by the Norwegian government. Following prolonged consultation with Norwegian authorities prior to announcing its withdrawal in July 2021, government pressure is also said to have been a factor (Justice for Myanmar, 2022).

TotalEnergies was also subjected to pressure from French authorities and European Union sanctions which played a role in its withdrawing in January 2022.

International pressure on Korean banks was much more limited. The international attention of civil society and the media was dominated by European companies, while Korean firms were more out of the fire under international scrutiny.

Chinese and Thai firms came under virtually no international pressure to exit, which was a function of home government policies that prioritized non-intervention or economic necessity over ethical concerns. This differential exposure to social consensus helps explain much of the variation found in corporate responses.

4.2.2 T2.2 Employee Protection and Local Responsibility

Mitigating international influence was another worry for local workers and communities whose livelihoods were tied to company operations. Staff of Telenor workers in Myanmar filed a petition against that withdrawal, since “our livelihoods are in jeopardy” (The

Irrawaddy, 2021). The withdrawal of the company ultimately impacted approximately 300 regular employees and thousands of indirect workers.

Korean banks specifically cited employee protection as their principal reason for remaining. A Shinhan Bank representative emphasized that “continuing operations rather than withdrawing was inevitable to ensure the employment stability and livelihood protection of local employees.” With hundreds of local workers relying on their work, Korean banks considered immediate, concentrated harm to employees more than diffuse, long-term damage from possible regime support.

TotalEnergies balanced this risk by offering all employees continued employment with the new operator (PTTEP) on an equal basis, keeping their status quo, but by also withdrawing, allowing all workers to have their work benefits while the company exited. This shows how employee protection and exit need not be incompatible where exit is planned in advance and carried out.

4.3 Theme 3: Exit Processes and Stakeholder Outcomes

4.3.1 T3.1 Employee Protection Measures

It found that how companies protected or failed to protect employees at exit was one of the key drivers of stakeholder outcomes. TotalEnergies practiced excellent employee service, ensuring that all workers were allowed to work with PTTEP on the same terms and conditions. This succession plan protected workers from the short-term danger that unemployment provoked and also continued their careers.

Telenor had taken a completely different approach. Selling to M1 Group came with a contract that offered severance and transition support, but left affected employees suffering working conditions, such as losing their salaries and being without steady employment. Workers did face the brunt of the controversial sale, with no way of claiming compensation if the situation

deteriorated, in the absence of anything that was enforceable and there were no protections that could work to protect workers. With

Kirin's approach of walking and pulling out slowly, the transition left employees in a state of long-lingering uncertainty as it took 21 months to ascertain whether they would get the new job in the future. On the other hand, the longer uncertainty itself was harm. Employees were unable to plan for the future or look for another job while the company's withdrawal was in question. By sticking around, a substantial number of Korean banks were able to provide jobs to hundreds of local workers; the downside is however an inextricable link with the military regime.

4.3.2 T3.2 Asset Disposition and Military Transfer

The ultimate disposal of corporate assets became crucial to ethical outcomes. TotalEnergies did not "take any financial compensation and gave away its assets," with the end goal of clean exit taking precedence over financial recovery, ensuring that its exit did not reinforce the regime.

Telenor took a much lower sale price of \$105 million, well below its total investment, though it was severely criticized when M1 Group's prior engagements with military-linked companies came to light. Even with M1 Group giving it guarantees and due diligence on human rights, the company had not been able to avoid the problematic associations of the purchasers, as there was also the worry that the company's asset could be an instrument of military interests.

Kirin endured the most complicated fate, being stripped of all control when Myanmar courts ruled that MEHL could purchase its stake in Myanmar Brewery. This imposition of succession meant that assets transferred to military-operated company, which ironically reinforced what the exit was supposed to protect—the exit was supposed to break. The case

illustrated that gradual withdrawal comes with unique dangers when local legal systems are dominated by or allied with military interests.

4.4 Theme 4: After-exit Effects and Legacies

4.4.1 T4.1 Community and Local Development

Exit decisions resonated far beyond company employees in local communities. TotalEnergies entered into a supplementary support agreement with PTTEP to maintain economic development in communities along the MGTC pipeline, thereby demonstrating that responsibility to long-supported communities is sustained after withdrawal. It preserved ties and support that otherwise would have been severed.

Telenor's transfer to M1 Group raised doubts about whether the new owner could also engage effectively with the community under a similar ownership agreement and whether there would be binding obligations to continue social programs. Kirin's forced departure meant a transfer of assets to MEHL, which could bolster the military's economic grip on communities rather than promoting local development.

Korean banks' continued support was the critical element that supported Korean companies' operations in Myanmar, indirectly enabling their businesses and local supply chains. While ethically challenged through close connection to the regime, the continued operation sustained economic activity that served local communities.

4.4.2 T4.2 Reputational and Legal Exposure Long Run

Companies face continuing reputational cost and could risk lawsuits on an exit basis. Telenor has been the subject of unrelenting criticism by Amnesty International, Human Rights Watch and other groups over its “irresponsible withdrawal” and controversial sale to M1 Group. Its reputational damage in some areas can affect its activities in other nations and with stakeholders worldwide.

TotalEnergies was criticized for having facilitated approximately \$500 million in revenue payments to the military junta before it withdrew, despite a mostly favorable evaluation of its exit program. The conduct continues to haunt its future reputation: this pre-exit behavior could soon have legal dimensions as the norms about corporate complicity mature.

Kirin's forced transfer to MEHL has caused longstanding reputational problems, wondering if the company had taken more steps in the pipeline to stop assets becoming military-controlled. Korean banks risk long-term reputational damage with Myanmar's democratization while scrutiny turns to companies who continued to function under the rule of the military. Chinese and Thai firms have dealt with more muted short-term reputational damage but could encounter future accountability demands.

4.5 Summary of Findings

Thematic analysis of six corporate cases uncovers four key trends. The first explains how corporate entry strategies and the degree of military entanglement shaped exit possibilities, with companies in direct joint ventures exhibiting more constraints than those in independent operations. Second, the drive for withdrawal decisions was the result of two conflicting pressures: the pressure of international social consensus, which leaned towards exit, and protectionism in employees leaning toward retention. Third, the kind of exit method, namely employee protection strategies and asset disposition, were found to matter more than the binary decision of exit or stay from the strategic decision of leaving. Fourth, the post-exit ramifications, whether community impact or long-term reputation risk, are ongoing and may also change ethical judgment about decisions over time.

These results were consistent with Hypothesis 3, that the impact of corporate exit is dependent not only on the exit itself but also on the mode, timing, and mechanism of exit. The cases illustrate that gradual, stakeholder-engaged exits produce the best exit outcomes

compared either to a swift abandonment or a long-term presence, which fosters regime complicity, even if these exits are associated with added complexity and cost to the withdrawing firm.

CHAPTER V: ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Addressing the Research Questions

This chapter discusses the findings presented in Chapter 4 and further describes theoretical and practical considerations. The analysis is structured around the four research questions directing our study. Section 5.1 supports all research questions by integrating case-study findings and employing Jones's moral intensity model. Section 5.2 provides a comparative analysis of the six cases, identifying patterns and divergences across countries and exit types. Section 5.3 discusses the theoretical consequences for B4P theory, Jones's model, and responsible exit literature. Finally, Section 5.4 forms the Responsible Exit Framework (REF) as a useful method for comprehending and steering corporate withdrawal decisions in conflict-affected countries.

5.1.1 RQ1: The Impact of Myanmar's Political Trajectory on Corporate Withdrawal Decisions

Myanmar's political evolution over decades that spanned from military rule (1962-2010) to partial liberalization (2011-2020) to the aftermath of a military coup in 2021, provided an ethical space for corporate withdrawal through three lenses: the configuration of entry structures, determinability of military disengagement, and the conditioning of stakeholder expectations.

First, decades of military rule established the institutional legacy that shaped corporate presence. The military gained significant economic dominance through such conglomerates as MEHL and MEC, monopolizing key industries. According to South and Lall (2023, p. 82), "foreign investors engaged in an environment in which economic reforms and continued human rights violations coexisted alongside the entrenched influence of military-linked

economic actors." This also meant that foreign firms engaging with Myanmar had to negotiate relationships with military-affiliated actors. TotalEnergies (1992) entered into a joint venture with MOGE, creating direct financial flows to the military. Kirin (2015) acquired a 55% share of Myanmar Brewery through partnership with MEHL. Telenor (2014) steered clear of forging direct partnerships but operated under military influence by way of licensing. Korean banks (2016-2019) intentionally bypassed direct military partnerships by creating stand-alone branches to do business with Korean businesses.

Second, the partial liberalization (2011-2020) opened both paths and ethical traps. Foreign investment moved under this hopeful "presence assumption" that corporate investment would back democratization — the basic premise of B4P theory. FDI peaked at 4.88 billion USD in 2019-20 (Figure 1.1), while telecommunications accounted for 8.7% of FDI (Figure 1.3). Telenor's entry, Kirin's acquisition and creation of Korean banks all showed a similar optimism. And yet they also further cemented ties with the military, by maintaining its economic influence, even in the face of political change, during this time.

Third, the coup in February 2021 radically changed the ethical climate, leaving corporate people "in a position to make tragic ethical choices" (Brenkert, 2021, p. 537). Ongoing operation meant giving material aid to an illegitimate regime; withdrawal posed a threat to local workers' welfare. This dilemma is particularly significant for the companies that operate direct military joint ventures themselves. TotalEnergies found that gas revenues flowed into MOGE through a fixed, unalterable payment structure. Kirin got entangled with the law when MEHL fought against dissolution. Telenor, which had not entered into direct joint ventures, did face tremendous international pressure as a state-owned entity. Korean banks, which escaped direct military connections, might have safeguarded employees and chose to keep working.

In summary, Myanmar's political course influenced decision-making regarding the withdrawal through political and structural forces: the institutional legacies of military financial and economic control left companies with varying degrees of military entanglement; the “presence assumption” of the liberalization era encouraged investment prior to political backlash; and the coup’s abrupt eruption forced companies to reexamine the boundaries of their established ethical frameworks. Businesses with joint military ventures on the ground underwent longer and more complicated exits, while those with their own operations could be more agile under international pressure.

5.1.2 RQ2: Analyzing Corporate Responses Through Jones's Moral Intensity Dimensions

Jones's (1991) six dimensions of moral intensity provide a powerful lens for understanding why companies responded differently to the Myanmar coup. Each dimension shaped ethical calculations in ways that explain the divergence between immediate exit, gradual withdrawal, and continued presence.

Social Consensus

Even after the coup, international consensus hardened, with the UN, EU, and US denouncing the regime and recommending corporate withdrawal. Pressure from home governments and civil society, coupled with direct intervention from Norway, left little room for maneuver for European companies, including Telenor’s decision-making. Korean banks faced less scrutiny, as global scrutiny was focused mainly on European companies. This difference is why European companies disappeared quickly, while Korean banks stayed.

Magnitude of consequences

Being a double-edged sword, continued activity risked serving the military through taxes and license fees while withdrawal risked devastating local workers and communities. Telenor’s

withdrawal targeted 300 regular employees and thousands of indirect ones, who petitioned against leaving and said "it will seriously hurt our livelihoods." European companies attributed greater weight to the support for the systemic regime; Korean banks put their employees direct interests at the forefront. These weightings highlight fundamental ethical disagreements over which of the three is really responsible.

Concentration of effect

Shedding light on this differentiation, The harms due to withdrawal focused on Myanmar workers who were employed directly by foreign companies, their families, and local suppliers. The harms of regime support were diffuse across Myanmar society, so that its severity was less immediately apparent. Focus on concentrated, visible harm (Korean banks) generally remained; those on diffuse, systemic harm (European firms) tended to retreat. This tension poses one of the most difficult dilemmas when it comes to ethical decision-making in conflict zones.

Probability of effect

While being introduced a lot of uncertainty into the calculations of corporates, funding for the regime from taxes was anticipated; the consequences of withdrawals were not. Telenor's purchase and sale to the M1 Group are examples of this risk: despite human rights due diligence, a buyer's military ties drew controversy, raising the potential for assets to bolster the regime. Kirin also battled an even harder dilemma of losing control when Myanmar courts ruled that MEHL was entitled to access its holdings. These examples show that the nature of withdrawal outcomes is inherently uncertain under conditions of institutional collapse.

Temporal immediacy

Withdrawal inflicted immediate harm on workers in unfavorable circumstances where

factories shuttered, wages suspended, livelihoods were imperiled for 24 hours. Cash flowed in and out of the regime through opaque channels over time. Those companies that were more interested in immediate harm (Korean banks) stayed put; those considering longer-term impact (European ones) left.

Proximity

European firms had more psychological proximity through heavy media coverage and civil society pressures at home. Korean firms' domestic scrutiny at home was low, so they felt more connected to local employees than to remote regime victims. This differential mediated other dimension to how companies weighted them.

As a whole, these dimensions reveal fundamental deficiencies in B4P theory when applied to authoritarian contexts. The theory's "presence assumption" that corporate presence plays a positive role in promoting peace, simply doesn't hold where the state itself promotes violence. B4P doesn't account for the dimensions of moral intensity pulling companies in opposite directions, resulting in tragic ethical choices in which no option is morally pure. The Myanmar cases show that the conduct of a responsible company demands consideration of multiple dimensions and that different arrangements may legitimately lead to different answers to what responsibility is being asked for.

5.1.3 RQ3: The Impact of Withdrawal Strategies on Local Stakeholders

The six cases examined in this study show that although the outcomes of corporate withdrawal decisions did depend on whether the firms exited or remained, they depended on how they approached the exit process, on the timing of exit, and on transfer of assets and protection of employees. These results support the Hypothesis 3 that gradual, stakeholder-engaged exits lead to better outcomes than either immediate abandonment or a continued presence that creates regime complicity.

For local employees, the outcomes varied dramatically across cases. TotalEnergies demonstrated that responsible exit is possible, despite withdrawal being inevitable. The company provided protection from the direct effects of unemployment by extending employment to all employees at PTTEP under the same conditions and terms. By contrast with Telenor's move out to M1 Group, which was thought to result in a deterioration in working conditions and insecurity in their jobs.

In spite of Telenor guaranteeing severance and transition facilities, the absence of any enforceable protections made workers suffer from the controversial sale, which was held up for 21 months and created confusion regarding their future jobs.

Korean banks (notwithstanding much resistance to the change) were able to keep hundreds of local workers employed despite their continued links to military authority. At home in the local supplier and community, the repercussions were no less considerable.

TotalEnergies had formed an additional support agreement with PTTEP to support economic development programs in communities along the MGTC pipeline to continue after its withdrawal, showing that the obligations of long supported communities don't end with withdrawal.

By contrast, the sale of Telenor to M1 Group had also sparked concern that the new owner would not maintain similar community engagement. Kirin's forced exit left assets flowing to MEHL, a military-owned conglomerate, while serving to strengthen the economic base of the regime rather than supporting local communities.

Korean banks' continued operations had provided infrastructure needed by Korean businesses operating in Myanmar, which indirectly supported local supply chains and business networks. One of the key factors in ethical outcomes turned out to be the transfer of assets. TotalEnergies sold off its shares "without any financial compensation," choosing clean

exiting instead of recovering financially.

Telenor accepted a much lower sale price of \$105 million, well below its total investment, but came under criticism after M1 Group's military connections turned out to be an issue. Kirin entirely lost control after Myanmar courts ruled that MEHL could claim its stake, which meant that assets transferred directly to a military entity. These cases illustrate that the final disposition of assets may be more important than the initial exit, when assessing the morality of investment practice. These results serve to guide the ethical review of corporate decisions in three respects.

These findings inform the ethical assessment of corporate decisions in three ways.

First, they demonstrate that the manner and process of exit matters more than the binary choice of whether to exit. TotalEnergies' rational, worker-centric exit was more ethically justifiable than Telenor's abrupt but poorly designed exit, while both companies ultimately departed.

Second, they show that staying can be ethically justified under particular circumstances, especially when businesses are not directly tied to the military and are willing to protect employees like Korean banks were.

Third, they note that asset disposal should be considered a fundamental aspect of responsible exit since transferring assets to military entities may also serve to strengthen the regime exit aims to isolate.

These conclusions suggest that ethical assessment must move beyond simple judgments of exit versus remain to consider the full complexity of how withdrawal is conducted and what consequences are produced for those most affected.

5.1.4 RQ4: Developing the Responsible Exit Framework (REF)

The preceding analysis of corporate responses to the Myanmar coup reveals that existing

frameworks are inadequate for guiding withdrawal decisions in conflict-affected countries. B4P theory's presence assumption does not provide any help when the decision to remain in business becomes ethically untenable. Brenkert's (2021) responsible exit framework provides a useful starting point, but to achieve its full potential, empirical grounding and contextual refinement are essential. Jones's (1991) model of moral intensity clarifies the ethical aspects of withdrawal, however, has not been formulated and applied into practice.

The Responsible Exit Framework (REF) seeks to address these limitations by taking account of these gaps and synthesizing the lessons from all three traditions as a single analytical tool. Its structure The REF is based on four principles, which are largely rooted in the Myanmar cases.

First, context matters. withdrawal processes cannot be evaluated without contextual knowledge of the political, economic as well as institutional environment companies are in. Second, structure influences options. The mode of entering the sector, its composition, and its track record with local actors act as determinants to limiting exit options for a company. Third, process determines outcomes. How a company withdraws in regards with the timing, transparency, and stakeholder engagement matters more for ethical assessment than the binary decision to exit or remain. Fourth, consequences bear the weigh. The ultimate disposition of assets, the fate of employees and the impact on local communities should be central to ethical appraisal.

The REF operationalizes these principles with a multi-faceted analytical process.

The first dimension presents contextual analysis: it identifies the nature of the conflict (state versus non-state violence), the extent of state capture, the legal and institutional environment, and the extent to which local actors rely on foreign investment. The Myanmar case studies illustrate state capture, where both political institutions and economic structures are

controlled by the military, has qualitatively distinctive ethical problems as compared to other conflict contexts.

The second dimension looks at corporate structure and entanglement: ownership (state versus private), way of entry mode (joint venture versus independent operation), degree of military links or bonds (direct and indirect links), and asset properties (liquid and fixed, transferable and stranded). Telenor's state-owned status made it more subject to international resistance while TotalEnergies' joint venture with MOGE imposed structural constraints on a potential break out; Kirin's partnership with MEHL resulted in legal entanglements; Korean banks, with their independent operations retained flexibility.

The third dimension uses Jones's six dimensions of moral intensity to examine the ethical implications of withdrawal in a systematic manner. The Myanmar cases suggest that these dimensions intersect in intricate ways: social consensus pressure can contradict magnitude of consequences calculations, proximity within stakeholder groups and temporal immediacy that can mask longer-term consequences. The REF offers a systematic framework to compare these competing perspectives rather than making false assumptions that they lead to a single right answer.

The fourth dimension includes stakeholder mapping and engagement: identify affected stakeholders (employees, suppliers, communities, and customers); find out, assess and design processes for meaningful consultation. Employee succession planning and local support agreements at TotalEnergies typify this framework and Telenor's lack of labor protections demonstrates what happens if this dimension is ignored.

The fifth dimension examines the disposition and legacy of assets: it relates to exploring transfer options (sale, abandonment, donation), prospective buyers (military connections, stakeholder commitment), and planning for post-exit follow-up. The divergent results of

TotalEnergies' clean exit, Telenor's disputed sale, and Kirin and the inevitable handover to MEHL testify to a vital point of this dimension.

My conclusion is that REF makes its own contribution to B4P scholarship when it extends beyond the presence/absence dichotomized choice to account for exit as a choice that has moral dimensions that requires a distinctive ethical construction. It operationalizes Jones's dimensions of moral intensity for actionable guidance and Brenkert's philosophical considerations toward actionable guidance, providing a tool to compare different processes across conflict settings. Most importantly, it recognizes that responsible corporate conduct in authoritarian environments may require accepting that no option is morally pure and that the measure of responsibility lies not in choosing the "right" option but in managing the chosen option with transparency, stakeholder engagement, and commitment to minimizing unavoidable harm.

5.2 Comparative Case Analysis

5.2.1 Comparison by Exit Type

The cases fall into three categories of response: immediate exit, gradual withdrawal, and continued presence. Each category shows characteristic patterns of drivers, processes, and outcomes.

Telenor and TotalEnergies both decided to withdraw within months of the coup.

However, they had markedly different exit processes. Telenor announced its exit in July 2021 and completed the sale to M1 Group in March 2022, a relatively rapid process of eight months. TotalEnergies announced its withdrawal in January 2022 and completed the exit in July 2022, a six-month process. The other factors that both companies noted were international pressure and human rights worries and reflected the high social consensus dimension of moral intensity. TotalEnergies guaranteed that all employees were retained at

the new operator on identical terms, continued community support programs through a supplementary agreement, and gave away its assets without any monetary payment. Telenor, which promised severance and transition support, embroiled itself in controversy after employees moved to M1 Group reportedly struggled to stay on the job, while the sale amid worries over links from the military appeared to carry over assets.

This comparison illustrates that leaving immediately does not equate to the right exit. What matters the most is the manner of withdrawal, especially employee protection and asset disposition instead of speed.

Kirin Holdings is the only case of gradual exit in this article. Its departure last fell in August 2021, but remained for 21 months; in November 2022, it did not formally exit, completing after a long period of time. This prolonged period of time was due to interlocking considerations: the difficulty in disassembling a jointly operated business arrangement where MEHL held military-owned MEHL, the involvement in Myanmar court proceedings, and opposition from military partner. The phased exit introduced an extended uncertainty for workers, who were unsure where their jobs stood at the time. In the end, Kirin lost its grip on its assets after Myanmar courts ruled that MEHL could buy its stake in Myanmar Brewery and transferred assets in a military-controlled manner.

This situation reveals that incremental withdrawal comes with unique risks to stakeholders, such as loss of control over asset disposition and longer uncertainty among stakeholders, even in the face of rationalizations for effective exit.

Korean banks, as well as Chinese companies and Thai businesses, decided to stay in Myanmar after the coup only for different reasons. Korean banks emphasized protecting employees, pointing to responsibility to hundreds of local workers, whose lives relied on ongoing operations. Chinese firms stayed for political and strategic reasons, reflecting the

Chinese government's non-interference principle and Myanmar's significance as a gateway to the Indian Ocean under the Belt and Road Initiative. Thai firms stayed mainly for economic reasons, chiefly energy security, as Thailand relies heavily on Myanmar gas for electrical power generation. These distinct motives generated diverse ethical considerations.

Korean banks' decision to stay despite not having direct military connections could be made on the basis of employee protection. Chinese firms were subjected to steeper international censure given their perceived backing of the military. The remaining of Thai companies was broadly accepted as structurally necessary because of energy dependencies.

This comparison illustrates the idea that the remaining is not separable; whether there are direct military links, which stakeholders are reliant on, and the motives behind their participation do shape the ethical analysis of remaining decisions.

5.2.2 Comparison by National Origin

European companies (Telenor and TotalEnergies) exhibited similar reaction patterns despite differences in their industry sectors and corporate structures. Both faced severe international pressure from home governments, EU institutions, and civil society. Both had a high degree of social consensus about the illegitimacy of the military regime and the necessity of a corporate withdrawal. While both exited ultimately, this had different results for interested parties. The fact that this pattern is taking shape also illustrates the powerful institutionalization of European corporate governance's human rights norms and the powerful ability of civil society pressure.

Japanese firms, characterized by Kirin Holdings, demonstrated a particular pattern, taking longer to deliberate and more closely intertwined with local bodies. Kirin's 21-month exit process is a marked contrast to European companies with 6-8 months that they could have gone. The very long timeline is an indication of its complex partnership structure, and reflects

the Japanese government's more cautious approach to the conflict with the Myanmar military. The outcome suggests that Japanese companies may face greater challenges in executing controlled exits when partnered with military entities.

Korean banks showed a pattern different from both European and Japanese firms. Despite a history of avoiding direct joint ventures with military organizations, they preserved a higher degree of flexibility in their response. Their decision to stay was more motivated by employee protection, not by politics or strategizing. The relatively low level of international scrutiny they faced reflects their somewhat smaller scale and the concentration of global civil society on European corporations. This pattern mirrors the peculiar positionality of middle power corporations, which function under different configurations of both stakeholder pressure and ethical expectation than their Western or larger Asian counterparts.

Chinese and Thai companies are examples when national interests take precedence over corporate ethical considerations. Chinese companies' remaining reflects state policy and strategic interests rather than corporate-level ethical deliberation. The remaining Thai companies reflect the structural economic dependencies that make exit from business virtually impossible.

These cases demonstrate that for some corporations, the exit/remain decision is not primarily an ethical choice, reflecting broader state interests or structural constraints.

5.2.3 Comparison by Corporate Structure

Corporate structure emerged as a critical determinant of exit opportunities and outcomes. For companies with joint ventures with military interests, the constraints were radically different from those on independent operations. TotalEnergies' MOGE joint venture, however, established structural barriers to exit, as gas sales are under a payment structure that made it virtually impossible to prevent funds from moving to the military. Kirin's cooperation with

MEHL led to legal entanglements that in the end led to losing control of their assets. Telenor, with the exception of its refusal of direct joint venture arrangements, was still operating under military control via licensing and regulatory mechanisms, and as a state-owned entity, in particular, was vulnerable to foreign pressure.

Korean banks were somewhat more independent, having set up their own branches rather than having joint ventures. This structural difference also explains why Korean banks could credibly frame staying as protective of employees instead of regime support.

Ownership structure was also significantly crucial. Telenor's status as a state-owned enterprise, with the Norwegian government holding a 54% stake, made it more susceptible to at-home government pressure than solely private companies. TotalEnergies was private but experienced pressure due to French government positions and EU sanctions. As a private Japanese company, Kirin had greater indirect government pressure, which is partly why it took a longer time to decide. As private banking, Korean banks responded mostly on regulatory guidance rather than direct government directive.

5.2.4 Summary of Comparative Findings

This comparative analysis yields several key findings. First, immediate exit does not equal responsible exit; the way you exit matters more than how fast you do so. Second, gradual withdrawal has its own set of risks, such as loss of control over asset disposition and prolonged uncertainty for stakeholders. Third, it is impossible to measure the 'remain' homogeneously, meaning that the direct presence or absence of military ties, stakeholder dependencies and motivations play an essential role in the ethical assessment. Fourth, national origin plays a major role in the response pattern, with European companies experiencing more institutional pressure, Japanese companies taking longer to deliberate and Korean banks occupying a specific middle power role, and Chinese and Thai companies

representing state interests. Fifth, the corporate structure, in particular direct joint ventures with military entities and the type of ownership, severely constrains exit possibilities and what results may be obtained from them. These results accentuate the importance of the multi-dimensional analytical framework developed in the Responsible Exit Framework.

5.3 Theoretical Implications

This section discusses the theoretical implications of the findings from the Myanmar case analysis for B4P theory, Jones's moral intensity model, and responsible exit theory.

5.3.1 Implications for B4P Theory

The Myanmar situation fundamentally problematizes the very assumption at the heart of B4P: the “presence assumption.”

From Fort and Schipani (2004) to Miklian and Katsos (2024), much of the B4P literature has explored the view that merely possessing corporate presence can help induce positive change in peace through creating jobs, fostering economic development, and facilitating stakeholder involvement. But 2021’s coup in Myanmar vividly demonstrates the collapse of this, then, or rather, the “presence assumption,” in cases in which the state itself becomes a cause of conflict.

First, a critical question arises with regard to the applicability of B4P theory in state capture contexts. Thus, as Breen (2024, p. 298) cautions, "when the state itself is a conflict driver, corporate peacebuilding efforts are not simply suppressed, but can be hijacked or weaponized as well." In Myanmar, the military had been able to dominate the entire economy through conglomerates like MEHL and MEC, while companies like TotalEnergies and Kirin were inescapably entangled with the military through joint ventures with these military-owned enterprises. In such cases, corporate presence did not contribute to peace but rather provided economic resources to the military regime.

Second, B4P theory demands some reexamination of the hypothesis that corporations can function as “neutral arbiters.” B4P theory began this way on the premise that business could promote the integration of the people in the economy through economic activities and remain politically neutral. But in the case of Myanmar, neutrality wasn’t an option for corporations. Operating under the military regime on an ongoing basis legitimated the regime, while withdrawing inflicted severe economic damages on local workers. Telenor CEO Sigve Brekke’s statement that “continuing operations could not be ethically justified” starkly conveys the illusion of neutrality.

Third, within its theoretical context B4P theory has systematically missed how to properly conceptualize “exit.” Exit has mainly been seen within the existing B4P literature as the failure of peacebuilding efforts to exit a situation, and there is very little theorization of ethical dimensions of exit. However, the Myanmar case exhibits how exit can be ethically permissible in some circumstances. TotalEnergies’ structured and responsible exit demonstrates that withdrawal is not simply abandonment but in fact the way to fulfill corporate ethical obligations.

Fourth, B4P theory requires more advanced conceptual tools and principles to differentiate between conflict situations. The Myanmar story of 'state capture' raises qualitatively different moral quandaries from traditional civil war or failed state settings. Theoretical exploration is needed on how corporate responsibility should be redefined when the state itself becomes an instrument of violence.

5.3.2 Implications for Jones's Moral Intensity Model

While Jones’s (1991) moral intensity model was a useful tool for understanding the varied responses of corporates in the Myanmar instance, many weaknesses of the model were also uncovered.

First, it remains to be explored how the six dimensions interact. The case of Myanmar revealed the intricate relationships between social consensus, magnitude of consequences, proximity, and concentration of effect in influence upon corporate decision-making. In Telenor, high social consensus (international pressure to withdraw) mattered more than the magnitude of consequences (harm to local workers) while for Korean banks the magnitude of consequences (employee livelihoods) mattered more than social consensus. These dimensions have importance and interactions must be theoretically described.

Second, the importance of the "proximity" dimension was particularly pronounced. We can argue that the differences in responses between European and Korean companies may be explained by the proximity dimension. European companies were hence high on psychological proximity due to intense pressure from civil society and media attention in their home countries, and Korean companies, a lower level, could have put in more emphasis on livelihood concerns of local workers. This demonstrates that proximity is not simply geographical distance but a social and psychological factor shaped by media, civil society, and home government pressure.

Third, the significance of "temporal immediacy" and "concentration of effect" dimensions was established. The consequences that were a consequence of withdrawal decisions exposed a tension between urgent and concentrated harm (local worker unemployment) and long-run and diffused harm (supporting the military regime). These dimensions demand the theoretical comprehension of the way decision-makers contemplate distinct time periods and distributions of harm.

Fourth, it has been clear that moral intensity dimensions may differ according to various cultural and institutional contexts. In fact, even in the same situation, European, Japanese, and Korean companies showed different perceptions of moral intensity, suggesting that the

moral intensity model needs to be extended to account for cultural diversity.

5.3.3 Implications for Responsible Exit Theory

This has demonstrated that Brenkert's (2021) responsible exit framework in the Myanmar case analysis provides empirical footing and leads to some key extensions.

First, verification was the empirical validity of the concept of the “tragic ethical choices.” Companies doing business in Myanmar were presented with dilemmas between unavoidable harms, indicating that Brenkert's theoretical approach can be applied to actual corporate decision-making contexts. In response, TotalEnergies declared that preventing funds from flowing to MOGE is "materially impossible", an example of how structural constraints can lead to tragic choices.

Second, i identified that "asset disposition" was a core component of responsible exit. Although Brenkert highlighted the importance of transparency on processes, timing, and stakeholder engagement, the Myanmar case shows that who acquires the assets is a fundamental element in the ethical review of exit. Telenor's sale to M1 Group, the asset transfer of Kirin to MEHL, and TotalEnergies' forfeiture of financial compensation all demonstrate the importance of asset disposition.

Third, there needs to be theoretical development on exit during conditions of "institutional void." Meyer and Thein (2023) contend that the downfall of the formal organizations of Myanmar resulted in companies having to resort to informal networks and ad hoc schemes. These types of institutional voids erode the minimal institutional infrastructure that Brenkert's framework presupposes, prompting a more challenging ethical approach.

Fourth, theoretical consideration of the distinct positionality of “middle power” corporations is needed. The Korean banks' case provided a different ethical story from Western ones, which implies that the responsible exit theory needs to be expanded to account for various

national contexts and corporate positionalities. Fifth, it was recognized that there was a need for an integrative framework around the process and outcomes of exit. Indeed, Telenor and TotalEnergies exited, but by different routes, different outcomes. This means that not only the exit decision but also how exit is done and what it leads to must be analyzed simultaneously.

5.3.4 Synthesis: Theoretical Foundations of the Responsible Exit Framework (REF)

Synthesizing the theoretical implications discussed above, the Responsible Exit Framework (REF) can be built on the following theoretical foundations.

First, it critically examines B4P theory's "presence assumption" and reconceptualizes exit as an ethically justifiable choice in authoritarian contexts such as state capture.

Second, it utilizes Jones's six dimensions of moral intensity as analytical lenses for actual exit decisions, particularly considering interactions among dimensions and differential perceptions across cultural contexts.

Third, it empirically extends Brenkert's responsible exit framework by integrating asset disposition, institutional void, and the distinctiveness of middle power corporations.

Fourth, it adopts a multi-dimensional approach that integratively evaluates both the process and outcomes of exit.

Built on these theoretical foundations, REF can function as an analytical tool applicable not only to the Myanmar case but also to other conflict-affected countries such as Ukraine, Ethiopia, and Afghanistan.

5.4 The Responsible Exit Framework (REF)

Building on the theoretical implications discussed in the previous section, this section develops the Responsible Exit Framework (REF) as a practical analytical tool for understanding and guiding corporate withdrawal decisions in conflict-affected countries. The REF integrates insights from B4P theory, Jones's moral intensity model, and responsible exit

theory, while addressing the six research gaps identified in Chapter 2.

5.4.1 Core Principles of the REF

First, context matters. It is only because of the political, economic, and institutional context in which firms are operating that withdrawal approaches can be assessed. The Myanmar case shows how state capture, where the military controls political institutions as well as economic forces, produces qualitatively distinct ethical problems than other conflict situations.

Second, options are formed by structure. The mode of entry, ownership structure of a company and historical involvement with local actors essentially limit its exit routes. When companies entered into direct joint ventures with military actors (TotalEnergies, Kirin), the exit was longer and more complex than with independent operations (Korean banks).

Third, outcome is determined by process. How a company decides to pull what they're doing in terms of the timing, transparency and engaging stakeholders, is more relevant to an ethical assessment than the binary decision to walk away or stay. Even though both companies ultimately departed, TotalEnergies' phased, employee-driven withdrawal was, as a matter of ethical principle, better than Telenor's brisk yet ill-managed exodus.

Fourth, consequences count. The ultimate disposition of assets, the fate of employees, and the impact on local communities need to be at the heart of ethical assessment. The divergent outcomes of TotalEnergies' clean exit, Telenor's contentious sale and Kirin's forced transfer to MEHL stress that asset disposition may weigh more than the initial exit decision.

5.4.2 The REF Analytical Framework

The REF operationalizes these principles through a five-dimensional analytical process:

Dimension 1: Contextual Analysis

This dimension examines the broader environment in which the company operates:

- Nature of conflict: State versus non-state violence, degree of state capture

- Political trajectory: Historical context, regime type, stability
- Legal and institutional environment: Rule of law, regulatory framework, institutional void
- Economic dependence: Local stakeholders' reliance on foreign investment
- International context: Sanctions, diplomatic pressure, global norm

Dimension 2: Corporate Structure and Entanglement

This dimension analyzes the company's specific characteristics and relationships:

- Ownership structure: State-owned versus private, home country influence
- Entry mode: Joint venture versus independent operation, partnership types
- Military linkage: Direct partnership, indirect relationships, licensing arrangements
- Asset characteristics: Liquidity, transferability, strategic importance
- Stakeholder dependencies: Employee count, supply chain integration, community relations

Dimension 3: Moral Intensity Assessment

This dimension applies Jones's six dimensions to evaluate the ethical weight of withdrawal options:

- Magnitude of consequences: Scale of harm/benefit to workers, communities, regime
- Social consensus: International and domestic pressure, normative expectations
- Probability of effect: Certainty of outcomes, risk assessment
- Temporal immediacy: Timing of consequences, short-term versus long-term impacts
- Proximity: Psychological distance to affected stakeholders
- Concentration of effect: Distribution of harm across populations

Dimension 4: Stakeholder Mapping and Engagement

This dimension identifies affected parties and designs consultation processes:

- Stakeholder identification: Employees, suppliers, communities, customers, government
- Vulnerability assessment: Dependence on company, alternative livelihoods
- Engagement mechanisms: Consultation, information sharing, grievance procedures
- Protection measures: Severance, transition support, community investment

Dimension 5: Asset Disposition and Legacy Planning

This dimension addresses the post-exit consequences and responsibilities:

- Transfer options: Sale, abandonment, donation, phased withdrawal
- Buyer assessment: Military links, stakeholder commitment, operational capacity
- Legal mechanisms: Contractual protections, human rights clauses
- Post-exit monitoring: Follow-up, accountability, remediation
- Legacy programs: Community support, development initiatives

5.4.3 The REF Decision Matrix

The REF synthesizes these five dimensions into a decision matrix that maps potential exit strategies against their likely consequences for different stakeholder groups. This matrix does not prescribe a single correct answer but rather illuminates the trade-offs inherent in tragic ethical choices, enabling companies to make more informed, transparent, and defensible decisions.

This matrix evaluates three exit strategies across five analytical dimensions. It does not prescribe a single correct answer but illuminates the trade-offs inherent in each option.

Dimension 1: Contextual Fit examines the external environment. Immediate exit fits high international pressure and strong sanctions. Gradual exit suits moderate pressure with complex local conditions. Remain fits low pressure and high local dependence.

Dimension 2: Corporate Structure assesses company characteristics. Immediate exit works

for independent operations with low military entanglement. Gradual exit suits joint ventures and legal constraints. Remain fits companies with no direct military links and high employee dependence.

Dimension 3: Moral Intensity applies Jones's six dimensions. Immediate exit aligns with high social consensus and long-term focus. Gradual exit allows balanced considerations. Remain prioritizes high concentration of effect and short-term protection.

Dimension 4: Stakeholder Impact focuses on affected parties. Immediate exit risks worker harm and uncertain asset fate. Gradual exit enables managed transition with extended uncertainty. Remain provides employee protection but risks regime complicity.

Dimension 5: Asset Outcome addresses asset disposition. Immediate exit risks military acquisition. Gradual exit allows controlled transfer. Remain involves no transfer but perpetuates ethical challenges.

Table 5.1 REF Decision Matrix: Mapping Exit Strategies

Dimension	Immediate Exit	Gradual Exit	Remain
Contextual Fit	High international pressure, strong sanctions	Moderate pressure, complex local context	Low pressure, high local dependence
Corporate Structure	Independent ops, low military entanglement	Joint ventures, legal constraints	No direct military links, employee-dependent
Moral Intensity	High social consensus, long-term focus	Balanced considerations	High concentration of effect, short-term focus
Stakeholder Impact	Potential worker harm, uncertain asset fate	Managed transition, extended uncertainty	Employee protection, regime support risk
Asset Outcome	Risk of military acquisition	Controlled transfer possible	No transfer, continued operation

Source: Author's compilation based on REF analysis

5.4.4 Application of the REF to the Myanmar Cases

Using the REF for the six cases reviewed in this paper shows the analytical advantage of the REF:

Telenor scored high on social consensus and proximity from its status as a state-owned company, and pressure from Norwegian civil society, which resulted in their immediate exit. Yet, its lack of commitment to address asset disposition (Dimension 5) led to high-profile turnover to M1 Group and minimal worker protection (Dimension 4).

Due to its joint venture with MOGE, TotalEnergies struggled with severe structural constraints (Dimension 2), rendering continuous operations ethically impossible. Its systematic focus on stakeholder engagement (Dimension 4) and asset disposition (Dimension 5) produced a cleaner exit. However, criticism continued to be put against pre-exit fund flows to the regime.

Kirin illustrates the complexities of gradual exit. The joint venture structure (Dimension 2) and legal entanglements extended the path, while poor control over asset disposition (Dimension 5) led to forced transfer to MEHL and strengthened the military regime.

Korean banks suffered low scores on social consensus (Dimension 3) because of little international scrutiny and as a result were able to concentrate on their employees' protection (Dimension 4). Without direct military ties (Dimension 2) they were less ethically weighted to stay in it although the long-term reputational risk persisted (Dimension 5).

Chinese and Thai corporations illustrate that context (Dimension 1) and structural relationships (Dimension 2) can take precedence over moral intensity, with political strategy and energy security, determining what is left to decide.

5.4.5 Practical Guidance for Corporations

Based on the REF analysis, the following practical guidance can be offered to corporations operating in conflict-affected countries:

Pre-entry phase:

- Conduct thorough due diligence on potential military entanglement

- Structure entry to maintain exit flexibility
- Develop contingency plans for sudden political change
- Establish stakeholder relationships early

During operations:

- Maintain transparent stakeholder engagement
- Document human rights due diligence
- Monitor political and institutional developments
- Build local capacity and resilience

Exit planning:

- Initiate stakeholder consultation early
- Assess multiple exit options and their consequences
- Identify responsible buyers or transfer mechanisms
- Plan for post-exit monitoring and legacy programs

Exit execution:

- Ensure transparent communication throughout
- Prioritize employee protection and transition support
- Secure contractual protections for asset disposition
- Maintain commitment to affected communities

5.4.6 Limitations and Future Development of the REF

Despite its thorough analytical framework, the REF has several limitations that merit mention and guidance for further development. First, the REF is mostly developed from Myanmar and may need to be extended in other forms of conflict. Subsequent research should be elaborated and adjust the framework by including different examples such as Ukraine, Ethiopia, and

Afghanistan. Second, the REF has five dimensions, which are qualitative responses that can differ among assessors. More quantitative indicators or scoring systems could improve the consistency and comparability. Third, the REF emphasizes corporate decision-making but does not fully address the role of home governments, international institutions, and civil society in exit outcomes. Multi-stakeholder views could be included in future iterations. Fourth, since some information is confidential or unavailable, the REF's application requires access to information that may not always be available, particularly in opaque conflict settings. Methodological development for dealing with imperfect data is also needed.

5.4.7 Conclusion: The Contribution of the REF

The Responsible Exit Framework developed in this study has several contributions to theory and practice. Theoretically, it also moves beyond the presence/absence binary of B4P to theorize exit as a morally significant choice for which there's moral infrastructure to support it. It also operationalizes elements of Jones's moral intensity dimensions for decision making in practice, as well as rendering Brenkert's philosophical framework into implementable advice. Methodologically, it is an instrument to aid in comparative analysis of various conflict types and types of enterprises. Practically, it provides businesses with a process for negotiating the tragic ethical decisions that authoritarian environments require of them.

Most importantly, the REF recognizes that responsible corporate behavior in an authoritarian context is also, and maybe even perhaps even mostly, a matter of acknowledging that no option is morally pure, and that responsibility does not entail making the 'right' decision but choosing and treating the right decision with transparency, involving stakeholders and doing what can be done to prevent suffering. The REF therefore provides not a formula for an easy answer, but the framework for asking better questions and making more defensible choices when confronted with impossible choices.

CHAPTER VI: CONCLUSION

6.1 Summary of Findings

The purposes of this study was to investigate how multinationals reacted to the moral issues raised by the 2021 coup in Myanmar and to create a framework to understand how firms respond to such ethical issues, and the guidance for responsible exit decisions during the time of conflict in a host country. Implementing qualitative document analysis of six cases of Telenor, TotalEnergies, Kirin Holdings, Korean banks, Chinese companies, Thai companies, and through the thematic analysis of Braun and Clarke, the study achieved several highlights of thematic analysis.

First, the study found that Myanmar political direction played an important role in corporate exit decision making. Decades of military command had been an institutional legacy that structured corporate presence, as companies were entering the era during different times under different degrees of military embroiling. TotalEnergies' 1992 joint venture with MOGE, Kirin 2015 MEHL joint venture, Telenor's independent launch in 2014, and Korean banks' establishment of their branches post 2016 each posed different constraints and opportunities following the 2021 coup. The 2011-2020 partial liberalization period did bring investment under the hopeful B4P theory "presence assumption," but that was flawed when the state itself became a source of violence. The coup's abrupt onset faced corporations with tragic ethical choices in which no decision was undertaken without moral consequences.

Second, Jones's six dimensions of moral intensity helped us to observe why firms reacted differently. European companies facing intense international pressure responded with quick withdrawal; Korean banks encountered weaker scrutiny as a result of social consensus. The force of magnitude of the repercussions provided conflicting calculations, with European

firms giving high scores to systemic regime backing, but Korean banks focusing on immediate employee welfare. Concentration of effect meant withdrawal harm was concentrated on Myanmar workers while regime support harm was dispersed across society: companies focused on concentrated visible harm to stay, with those focused on diffused systemic harm to migrate away. The probability of effect left serious uncertain outcomes, evident in Telenor's high-profile sale of M1 Group and Kirin's loss of control to MEHL. Temporal immediacy generated differential urgency calculations, with companies sensitive to immediate suffering staying there and those concerned with long-term consequences leaving. Proximity accounted for European and Asian variation, with European firms facing psychological closeness through media attention, and Korean firms feeling closer to their local staff.

Third, the consequences for local stakeholders were not only determined, according to the researchers, by whether to exit or stay; rather, they were determined by how they handled it. TotalEnergies's responsible exit was effective when it offered all workers "the same terms of employment as before" while also continuing its community support. Telenor's quick and precipitated exit caused degradation of worker welfare, and contentious transfer of assets. Kirin's gradual departure engendered prolonged uncertainty and, in the end, solidified the military regime through involuntary asset transfers. Korean banks' decision to protect worker livelihoods but trade off continued interdependence with regime. Asset disposition proved to be a key factor determining the ethical outcomes of business, as TotalEnergies' clean exit contrasted sharply with Telenor's contested sale and Kirin's forced transfer.

Fourth, the analysis revealed fundamental deficiencies in B4P theory when applied to authoritarian contexts. The theory's "presence assumption" fails to account for situations that maintain violence by continuing on regardless of its impact. If presence is no longer ethically

feasible, B4P's failure to consider exit as a morally meaningful option fails to offer corporate decisionmakers direction. Jones's model of moral intensity, while strong from analytical aspect, does need to be operationalized to provide decision making practices for operation. Brenkert's responsible exit framework, although valuable starting points, needs empirical foundation and contextual refinement.

Finally, These findings ultimately led to the Responsible Exit Framework, a critical, multifaceted analytical framework with elements of situational awareness, corporate structure assessment, moral compass appraisal of potential corporate actors, stakeholder analysis, and alternative asset planning. The REF offers corporates, policymakers, and scholars a systematic guide to grappling with these tragic ethical choices endemic to authoritarianism.

6.2 Contributions and Implications

This study makes several contributions to theory, methodology, and practice, with implications for corporations, policymakers, and international organizations.

6.2.1 Theoretical Contributions

This work advances B4P theory by critically diagnosing its primary 'presence assumption' and demonstrating its inability to adapt well in an authoritarian context where the state becomes a driver of violence itself. While B4P literature has often concentrated on what role a corporate presence can play in setting the tone for peace-making, the current study argues that the continuation of business in contexts like Myanmar does not help in promoting peace and in fact can paradoxically reinforce illegitimate regimes and disrupt peacebuilding efforts. By re-conceptualizing exit as a morally significant choice and not merely failure or retreat, the research broadens B4P theory's analytical horizons to capture the entire corporate engagement's life cycle in conflict zones.

In addition, this study extends on Jones' theory of moral intensity, employing it to real

corporate exit decisions and revealing the complex interactions of the six dimensions. This analysis shows that social consensus, magnitude of consequences, proximity, temporal immediacy, probability of effect, and concentration of effect do not operate in isolation but interact in a way that impacts ethical calculations. The fact that proximity is socially constructed through media coverage and civil society pressure and not simply a matter of geographical distance contributes to deepening our knowledge about this dimension.

Furthermore, it demonstrates how cultural and institutional contexts shape perceptions of moral intensity, arguing that the application of the model needs to be more culturally sensitive. Also, the study offers empirical support for Brenkert's philosophical framework and multiple important extensions to responsible exit theory. Asset disposition as an important component to responsible exit provides an important insight not found in extant frameworks. Institutional void situations illustrate the ways that the absence of functioning legal and regulatory systems hinders responsible exit and pushes for more complicated ethical responses. This focus on middle power corporations, especially as they relate to Korean banks, raises further consideration of ethical potential and limitation that are driven by national context and corporate positionality.

6.2.2 Methodological Contributions

Methodologically, this study presents the utility of qualitative document analysis for sensitive research in contexts of conflict where access is restricted or not possible. Through methodical use of corporate reports, international organization documents, NGO publications, and media sources, the work demonstrates how rich, multi-perspectival data can be produced from sources other than primary data collection. The use of Braun and Clarke's thematic investigation of these multiple sources offers a case of systematic qualitative study in difficult circumstances.

The comparative case-based design, comprising six cases in five countries across three continents, highlights the need for cross-national analysis to elucidate how contextual aspects contribute to corporate behavior. With European, Japanese, Korean, Chinese, and Thai firms the research captures the difference that single-country studies would overlook, pointing out how the characteristics of home countries affect the responses of firms to similar ethical dilemmas.

6.2.3 Practical Implications

This study provides several lessons for the corporate entities working in the countries hit by conflict. First, companies should do proper due diligence on possible military entanglement prior to entry and structure their operations in a way that allow for exit flexibility. The divergent experiences of TotalEnergies and Kirin with their direct joint ventures and Korean banks with independent operations reflect the effect of mode on exit. The other is that companies should establish contingency plans against abrupt political change and consult with stakeholders early when exit becomes necessary. TotalEnergies' robust employee protection and community-based intervention schemes can serve as an example of responsible exit planning. The third lesson: Companies need to be particularly careful about the disposal of their assets to prevent one step in the process that sellers and buyers or transferees can perpetuate rather than reverse. The case of Telenor and its controversial sale of the M1 Group, and later Kirin's forced transfer to MEHL, demonstrates the repercussions of ignoring this factor.

For policymakers, the research suggests the need to bring clear guidance to companies in conflict environments. Norwegian, French, Japanese, and Korean companies illustrate how home government positions impact company actions. Policymakers must therefore create coherent mechanisms that strike a balance between pressuring for moral behavior and

acknowledging that corporations make tragic choices. International sanctions need to be structured according to their differing effects on various firms across many different structures and entanglements.

For institutions on the international level, it reflects the importance of the ongoing construction of normative frameworks that should guide the conduct of business in regions of conflict. While the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights contain the necessary framework, they provide relatively little guidance about the exit scenarios. OECD and UN Human Rights Council, for example, should provide guidance on responsible exit with regard to disposition of assets, protection of the employee, and post-exit monitoring of the organization.

6.2.4 Implications for Middle Power Corporations

The study's focus on Korean banks reveals distinctive challenges facing middle power corporations in conflict zones. Unlike European companies with strong home government pressure and civil society scrutiny, and unlike Chinese companies operating under state direction, Korean corporations navigate a middle space characterized by moderate pressure, limited guidance, and employee-focused ethical narratives. This finding suggests that middle power corporations require tailored frameworks that recognize their distinctive positionality rather than simply applying Western-derived ethical standards.

6.3 Limitations of the Study

Although this study also presents important findings, a few limitations should be carefully taken into account.

First, the present study depends solely on secondary sources of data. As a result of the sensitive nature of this Myanmar context and lack of accessible data, no direct interviews with corporate leaders, local stakeholders, or government authorities were done. While the

analysis used published interview data from academic studies, NGO reports, and media resources, this cannot fully address this primary data development. Secondary sources provide unique views, which, in turn, may capture prioritization and bias of authors more than the diversity of stakeholder experience.

Second, the study's narrow focus on six cases, while allowing comparative analysis, does not allow for generalizing any of the findings. Telenor, TotalEnergies, Kirin, Korean banks, Chinese companies, and Thai companies' experiences may not be reflective of those of companies in other industries, countries, or conflict situations. Corporations in industries such as extractives, manufacturing, and finance may be subject to certain restrictions and opportunities. Firms from countries that have distinct political systems, economic structures, and cultural orientations might react to comparable ethical quandaries differently.

Third, the study's timeframe, spanning events from the 2021 coup to 2026, does not cover the longer-term ramifications of corporate withdrawal decisions. Workers transferred to new operators' ultimate fate and the long-term effects on local communities. The forced transfer of Kirin to MEHL, for instance, has ramifications for Myanmar's political economy well beyond the study scope.

Fourth, the study design, despite being relatively comprehensive, inevitably oversimplifies complex realities. Jones's six dimensions of moral intensity, applied systematically across cases, may not capture the full texture of ethical decision-making in situations of radical uncertainty. As structured as the REF's five dimensions provide, however, the tragedy of choices where all choices involved catastrophic losses cannot be eliminated.

Lastly, perhaps through the centrality given to corporate decision-making over various groups within communities, the agency of local stakeholders may be underemphasized. Though the analysis explored consequences for workers, suppliers, and communities, it did not

comprehensively investigate how these stakeholders shaped corporate responses through action, negotiation, and resistance. Telenor employees' petition against withdrawal was a kind of agency that influenced decisions by the company, but was overruled.

6.4 Directions for Future Research

These limitations indicate multiple opportunities for future studies.

First, primary data collection with corporate decision-makers, local stakeholders, and government officials, when access is feasible, is of first concern for future studies. With Myanmar's political situation evolving, researchers might have the chance to interview those directly involved in withdrawal decisions, including perspectives not found in secondary sources. Comparative studies spanning different conflict contexts could investigate how such dilemmas are realized in various settings.

Second, the research needs to be widened in scope including additional cases with corporations from more diverse countries and sectors. Research on companies from India, Singapore, or other ASEAN countries may reveal regional trends. The exploration of extractive industries beyond oil and gas, manufacturing beyond beer production, and services beyond banking would illuminate sector-specific trends. Research on firms that performed alternative responses such as restructuring operations rather than simply exiting or remaining could provide additional insights into the strategic choices they had to make.

Third, longitudinal analyses that track the long-term effects of withdrawal decisions could help with the short-term focus of this study. Over the years, following workers who had been transferred to new operators, tracking community development in areas where exit has caused its effects and tracing what happens when corporate assets are disposed of or handed over could shed light on consequences that are invisible in shorter-term analysis. Such research would also shed light on how moral evaluation of decisions might change when full

consequences become obvious.

Fourth, more sophisticated analytic tools for the interpretation of ethical decision-making under radical uncertainty should be developed for future studies. Application of the REF to more cases, development of quantitative indicators for its dimensions, and testing of its utility within the context of corporate decision-makers would add to its practical utility. Comparative studies to develop the REF in a wider range of conflict contexts may evaluate the generalizability of the method and identify necessary modifications.

Fifth, research needs to pay more respect to the empowerment of local actors in the formation of corporate responses. Research focusing on how workers, suppliers and communities organized, protested, negotiated and reconfigured themselves around corporate decisions could highlight parts of power and resistance that corporate-centric analyses can downplay. These studies are also a vital tool to shed light on how populations who are affected can better get involved in decisions that will affect their lives.

Sixth, comparative studies about home government policies regarding corporate behavior in conflict-affected regions as well as the ways in which different regulatory paradigms have implications for these types of outcomes could also be helpful. To that point we do not yet provide detailed insights into Norwegian, French, Japanese, Korean, Chinese and Thai governments, yet analyses might help us gain insight into the influence of political systems, economic structures and historical relations on corporate behavior. This type of research may help find better policies to shape a more sustainable corporate behavior and future regulations.

Seventh, the applicability of the REF to other conflict-affected countries, including Ukraine, Ethiopia and Afghanistan requires studying for potential future research. To test for potential generalizability in more than a handful of different situations one would evaluate the framework, and determine if there needs to be adaptations to fit into different forms of

conflict, political systems, and forms of economy. Such comparative research could help us build a genuinely universal framework for understanding and informing corporate withdrawal decisions.

6.5 Concluding Remarks

This study began from the recognition that peace is not a unilateral concept but a multi-layered and complex phenomenon. The 2021 Myanmar coup confronted multinational corporations with unprecedented ethical challenges, revealing the inadequacy of existing frameworks for guiding withdrawal decisions. Through systematic analysis of six cases and development of the Responsible Exit Framework, this study has sought to contribute to more nuanced, context-sensitive understanding of corporate responsibility in conflict zones.

The findings demonstrate that ethical corporate behavior in authoritarian environments necessitates a deeper analysis that transcends the binary choice of exiting or staying. It is essential to explore the intricate dynamics of how withdrawal is executed and its resulting impacts. The findings highlight that organizations with varying backgrounds, frameworks, and connections encounter distinct ethical options and limitations. Furthermore, they emphasize that factors such as asset management, employee safeguarding, and stakeholder involvement are equally significant as the primary decision to either exit or stay.

Most importantly, this study has tried to shed light on the tragic nature of the decisions that corporations are forced to make in places like Myanmar. In such situations, no option is morally pure. Responsibility doesn't come from picking the 'right' choice, but rather caring for that choice in a transparent way that involves all stakeholders and aims to reduce inevitable damage. The Responsible Exit Framework provides not a formula for facile answers, but a tool for asking better questions and making more defensible decisions in the face of impossible choices.

While millions of lives in Myanmar and other affected countries are being transformed and impacted by conflict, the question of how corporations should be responding will remain an urgent one. This study hopes to contribute to ongoing efforts to develop frameworks, policies, and practices that support responsible corporate conduct and ultimately, the pursuit of peace.

REFERENCES

- Berman, M., 2022. Corporate exit strategies in conflict zones: The Myanmar dilemma. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 179(3), pp.721–738. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-021-04877-y>
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V., 2006. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), pp.77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Breen, M., 2024. The limits of business-for-peace: Rethinking corporate responsibility in authoritarian contexts. *Business & Society*, 63(2), pp.289–315. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00076503231157342>
- Brenkert, G.G., 2021. Responsible exit: A new framework for corporate withdrawal from conflict-affected areas. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 31(4), pp.523–551. <https://doi.org/10.1017/beq.2020.33>
- Creswell, J.W. and Clark, V.L.P., 2017. *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. 3rd ed. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Directorate of Investment and Company Administration (DICA), 2025. *Myanmar investment statistics report 2024–2025*. Naypyidaw: DICA.
- EarthRights International, 2022. *TotalEnergies and Chevron's Myanmar exit: A victory for the people of Myanmar*. [online] Available at: <https://www.earthrights.org> (Accessed: 10 March 2026).
- E24, 2021. *Telenor fikk ordre om å stenge nettet i Myanmar*. [online] Available at: <https://www.e24.no> (Accessed: 10 March 2026).
- Fort, T.L. and Schipani, C.A., 2004. *The role of business in fostering peaceful societies*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511616684>

- Frontier Myanmar, 2025. *Foreign investment trends in Myanmar: Sectoral analysis*. [online] Available at: <https://www.frontiermyanmar.net> (Accessed: 12 March 2026).
- GSMA Intelligence, 2022. *Myanmar telecommunications market report*. [online] Available at: <https://www.gsmaintelligence.com> (Accessed: 10 March 2026).
- Human Rights Watch, 2022. *Myanmar: Corporate complicity in military atrocities*. [online] Available at: <https://www.hrw.org> (Accessed: 10 March 2026).
- Jones, T.M., 1991. Ethical decision making by individuals in organizations: An issue-contingent model. *Academy of Management Review*, 16(2), pp.366–395. <https://doi.org/10.2307/258867>
- Justice for Myanmar, 2022a. *Telenor's reckless exit: How Telenor sold Myanmar operations to military-linked M1 Group*. [online] Available at: <https://www.justiceformyanmar.org> (Accessed: 10 March 2026).
- Justice for Myanmar, 2022b. *Military-owned MEHL and its business partnerships*. [online] Available at: <https://www.justiceformyanmar.org> (Accessed: 10 March 2026).
- Kirin Holdings, 2021. *Notice regarding impairment loss on Myanmar business*. [Press release] 31 August. Available at: https://www.kirinholdings.com/en/newsroom/release/2021/0831_01.html (Accessed: 12 March 2026).
- Kirin Holdings, 2022. *Annual report 2022*. [online] Available at: https://www.kirinholdings.com/en/investors/library/annual_report/ (Accessed: 12 March 2026).
- Kotra, 2025. *미얀마 투자 현황 및 전망 보고서*. [online] Available

at: <https://www.kotra.or.kr> (Accessed: 12 March 2026).

- Meyer, K.E. and Thein, H.H., 2023. MNE exit from Myanmar: Institutional collapse and strategic responses. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 54(4), pp.612–635. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41267-022-00587-1>
- Miklian, J., 2017. The business-peace nexus: A critical assessment. *Business and Politics*, 19(2), pp.185–213. <https://doi.org/10.1017/bap.2016.17>
- Miklian, J. and Katsos, J.E., 2024. The business–peace nexus: A critical assessment and research agenda. *Journal of Business Research*, 175, p.114132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2024.114132>
- Mobile World Live, 2022. *Blog: The last mobile greenfield fades, what is next?* [online] Available at: <https://www.mobileworldlive.com> (Accessed: 10 March 2026).
- Myanmar Investment Commission, 2025. *Cumulative investment by country report (February 2025)*. Yangon: MIC.
- New Age BD, 2026. *Japan's Kirin cuts ties with Myanmar military-owned firm*. [online] Available at: <https://www.newagebd.net> (Accessed: 12 March 2026).
- Oetzel, J., Westermann-Behaylo, M., Koerber, C., Fort, T.L. and Rivera, J., 2010. Business and peace: Sketching the terrain. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 89(4), pp.351–373. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-010-0411-2>
- Rest, J.R., 1986. *Moral development: Advances in research and theory*. New York: Praeger Publishers.
- Reuters, 2021. *Telenor to sell Myanmar business amid coup fallout*. [online] 8 July. Available at: <https://www.reuters.com> (Accessed: 10 March 2026).
- Reuters, 2022. *TotalEnergies and Chevron exit Myanmar gas field*. [online] 21 January.

Available at: <https://www.reuters.com> (Accessed: 10 March 2026).

- South, A. and Lall, M., 2023. Myanmar's business community and the 2021 coup: Between complicity and resistance. *Contemporary Southeast Asia*, 45(1), pp.78–103. <https://doi.org/10.1355/cs45-1c>
- Telenor Group, 2021a. *Telenor to exit Myanmar*. [Press release] 8 July. Available at: <https://www.telenor.com/media/press-release/telenor-to-exit-myanmar> (Accessed: 12 March 2026).
- Telenor Group, 2021b. *Sustainability report 2021*. [online] Available at: <https://www.telenor.com/sustainability/reports/> (Accessed: 12 March 2026).
- Telenor Group, 2021c. *Q2 2021 earnings release*. [online] Available at: <https://www.telenor.com/investors/reports/> (Accessed: 12 March 2026).
- Telenor Group, 2022. *Annual report 2022*. [online] Available at: <https://www.telenor.com/investors/reports/2022/annual-report-2022/> (Accessed: 12 March 2026).
- Thein, H.H., Meyer, K.E. and Breen, M., 2024. Eight propositions for responsible exit from conflict zones. *Journal of Business Ethics*, forthcoming.
- The Irrawaddy, 2021. *Telenor Myanmar employees protest planned exit*. [online] 15 July. Available at: <https://www.irrawaddy.com> (Accessed: 10 March 2026).
- The Irrawaddy, 2022. *Telenor Myanmar workers protest against new owner's salary cuts*. [online] 12 April. Available at: <https://www.irrawaddy.com> (Accessed: 10 March 2026).
- TotalEnergies, 2022a. *Myanmar: TotalEnergies to withdraw from the Yadana field*. [Press release] 21 January. Available at: <https://totalenergies.com/news/press-releases/20220121-myanmar-totalenergies-withdraw-yadana-field> (Accessed: 12 March

2026).

- TotalEnergies, 2022b. *Annual report 2022*. [online] Available at: <https://totalenergies.com/investors/publications-and-events/annual-report> (Accessed: 12 March 2026).
- United Nations Human Rights Council, 2024. *Report of the Independent International Fact-Finding Mission on Myanmar (A/HRC/55/CRP.2)*. Geneva: United Nations.
- Wikipedia contributors, 2026. Telenor Myanmar. In: *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*. [online] Available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Telenor_Myanmar (Accessed: 15 March 2026).
- World Bank, 2022. *Myanmar economic monitor: Coping with conflict*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank Publications. <https://doi.org/10.1596/37564> (Accessed: 15 March 2026).

Corporate Reports

- Telenor Group. (2021). Sustainability Report 2021.
- Telenor Group. (2022). Annual Report 2022.
- TotalEnergies. (2022). Annual Report 2022.
- TotalEnergies. (2022). Press Release: Myanmar Withdrawal (Jan 21, 2022).
- Kirin Holdings. (2021). Notice on Myanmar Business (Aug 31, 2021).
- Kirin Holdings. (2022). Annual Report 2022.
- Shinhan Bank. (2017-2021). Annual Reports.
- KB Kookmin Bank. (2017-2021). Annual Reports.
- Woori Bank. (2017-2021). Annual Reports.

International Organization Reports

- United Nations Human Rights Council. (2024). Report of the Independent International Fact-Finding Mission on Myanmar (A/HRC/55/CRP.2).
- World Bank. (2022). Myanmar Economic Monitor: Coping with Conflict.
- OECD. (2023). Responsible Business Conduct in Conflict-Affected Areas.

NGO Reports

- Justice for Myanmar. (2022). Telenor's Reckless Exit.
- Justice for Myanmar. (2022). Military-owned MEHL and Its Business Partnerships.
- Amnesty International. (2022). Myanmar: Telenor's Irresponsible Exit.
- Human Rights Watch. (2022). Myanmar: Corporate Complicity in Military Atrocities.
- EarthRights International. (2022). TotalEnergies and Chevron's Myanmar Exit.

Government and Institutional Data

- Directorate of Investment and Company Administration (DICA). (2025). Myanmar Investment Statistics Report 2024-2025.
- KOTRA. (2025). 미얀마 투자 현황 및 전망 보고서.
- Myanmar Investment Commission. (2025). Cumulative Investment by Country Report (Feb 2025).

News Media Sources

- Reuters. (2021-2022). Various articles on Telenor, TotalEnergies, and Myanmar.
- The Irrawaddy. (2021-2022). Various articles on corporate responses to Myanmar coup.
- Financial Times. (2021-2022). Various articles on Myanmar business environment.

- Nikkei Asia. (2021-2022). Various articles on Kirin and Japanese companies in Myanmar.
- BBC News. (2021-2022). Various articles on Myanmar coup and corporate responses.
- Frontier Myanmar. (2025). Foreign investment trends in Myanmar.
- Mobile World Live. (2022). Blog: The last mobile greenfield fades.
- E24. (2021). Telenor fikk ordre om å stenge nettet i Myanmar.
- New Age BD. (2026). Japan's Kirin cuts ties with Myanmar military-owned firm.

APPENDIX A: CODING FRAMEWORK

In this study, thematic analysis was conducted following Braun & Clarke (2006) approach by systematic coding of documents in order to identify recurring themes and patterns. It progressed through rigorous, iterative engagement with the data starting from descriptive codes to analytical themes.

The first main theme identified was exit type, encompassing three codes: immediate exit, gradual withdrawal, and continued presence. Immediate exit was applied to companies such as Telenor and TotalEnergies, which had announced withdrawals and completed them within a few months of the coup. Kirin had a 21-month process of gradual withdrawal that included legal proceedings and lengthy negotiations. Continued presence was applied to Korean banks, Chinese enterprises, and Thai enterprises that stayed in Myanmar after the coup.

The second theme, decision drivers, captured the forces that influence company decisions. Codes included international pressure, which denotes sanctions and diplomatic condemnation; reputational risk, related to brand image and stakeholder perceptions; employee protection, the livelihoods of local workers should be given high priority; economic factors, including financial losses and the market; legal constraints, incorporating contractual obligations and court proceedings; and home government influence which reflects the impact of domestic policies and pressures.

The third theme is on the influence of all stakeholders, with documented consequences for affected groups. Employee welfare included the impact on the means of livelihood and working environment. Job security was associated with job stability before, during and following exit decisions. Community support referred to corporate initiatives helping communities. Local businesses reliant on foreign companies were impacted by the disruption of the supply chain. Local economy reflected larger economic consequences of corporate

decisions.

The fourth theme, military entanglement, evaluated the ties between enterprises and Myanmar's military. Direct joint venture applied to companies such as TotalEnergies and Kirin with formal partnerships with military-owned entities. Telenor had an indirect relationship with the military, functioning under the auspices of licensing without a formal partnership. Licensing agreements also documented regulatory relations with military-controlled authorities. No military connection applied to Korean banks that intentionally refused to cooperate with military organizations. State capture was the broad context in which the military had dominance of both the institutions of politics as well as the structures of economics.

The fifth theme was asset disposition or the fate of corporate assets after they exit. Sale to third party applied to Telenor sale to M1 Group. Kirin's forced transfer to MEHL represented asset transfer. TotalEnergies' exit without compensation contrasted with Telenor's acceptance of reduced sale price, marking financial compensation. Abandonment was applied to cases when there was no transfer of assets. However, court proceedings took time — forced transfer demonstrated Kirin's loss of control.

The sixth theme involved the impact of home government roles, the examination of how local home country policies had an impact on corporate choices. Direct pressure applied to Norway's influence on Telenor. Japan's cautious approach featured diplomatic guidance. TotalEnergies' compliance with EU measures was significantly influenced by sanctions alignment. Korea's neutral view reflected a mindset of giving banks autonomy to make decisions. Non-interference expressed China's policy of not intervening with corporate matters.

The seventh theme, corporate structure, analyzed organizational features influencing

decision-making. State-owned with 54% Norwegian government ownership applied to Telenor. TotalEnergies, Kirin, and Korean banks were private. Joint venture describes TotalEnergies' partnership with MOGE, and Kirin with MEHL. Independent operation applied to Korean banks' branches. Ownership structure affected companies' responsiveness to competing pressures.

The eighth theme examined each case in the light of Jones' dimensions of moral intensity. Social consensus captured global agreement on regime illegitimacy. The magnitude of consequences weighed injury to workers against regime support. Proximity assessed psychological distance to affected populations. Temporal immediacy differentiated between immediate and delayed consequences. Probability of effect assessed how certain outcomes were made of a given time. Concentration of effect analyzed the distribution of the harm across populations.

APPENDIX B: TIMELINE OF MAJOR EVENTS

Myanmar's long-evolving political history over sixty years also played an important role in determining the environment in which multinational enterprises would thrive, only to face withdrawal decisions. This timeline follows the main events from the start of the military regime until the coup in 2021 and its aftermath.

The rule of the military started in 1962 when General Ne Win led a coup by military, paving the way for more than 50 years of authoritarian rule. In 1988, a new military junta emerged following massive pro-democracy uprisings, entrenching the dominance of the military over the political and economic institutions. The refusal of the junta to respect election results in 1990, when the National League for Democracy won by a landslide, further illustrated the military's insistence to uphold power at any cost through authoritarian means.

Foreign companies started entering Myanmar in spite of the authoritarian regime during this time of military command. TotalEnergies came into Myanmar in 1992 with the Yadana gas field project - a partnership with the state-owned Myanmar Oil and Gas Enterprise - that would generate ethical quandaries down the line.

The 2010s had brought with them the hopes for democratic transition. The 2010 saw a general election and Thein Sein's election, followed by a partial opening up and democratic reforms in 2011. This opening drew large foreign investment, expecting corporate participation to facilitate the democratization agenda. A number of large companies were included in this opening.

Telenor received a telecommunications license and ventured into Myanmar in 2014, emerging as the second-biggest mobile operator. In 2015, Kirin obtained a 55 per cent share of Myanmar Brewery by establishing a joint venture with military-owned Myanmar Economic Holdings. Korean banks also followed, with Shinhan Bank getting approval in

2016, KB Kookmin Bank in 2017 and Woori Bank in 2018, establishing separate, rather than joint ventures with military units, branches. In 2019-20, foreign direct investment in Myanmar reached its peak of 4.88 billion USD, suggesting international confidence in the country's direction was higher for the last five years. But after the National League for Democracy's general elections in 2020, and after the military claimed fraud without evidence, tensions were rising.

The liberalization period concluded on Feb. 1, 2021 after a military coup violently quashed the progressive democratization and coup led into power by the State Administration Council and captured civilian leaders of Myanmar at once. In March 2021, Telenor said it was deeply concerned about the situation, and in June Kirin suspended a repayment of dividends to MEHL in an effort to stop profits flow to the military.

Corporate exits began in July 2021 when Telenor declared withdrawal on July 8. Kirin stated that it would withdraw in August 2021, leading to a lengthy legal process. TotalEnergies withdrew from the Yadana field on January 21, 2022; their exit was completed on July 20, after the contractual notice period.

Throughout 2022, such withdrawal processes have had different results. Telenor sold its shares in March to M1 Group, criticized for the military ties of the M1 Group's buyers. Kirin petitioned Myanmar courts in February to dissolve its joint venture, but in November the court ruled that MEHL could acquire Kirin's stake, forcing the company to complete withdrawal on November 30 with assets transferred to the military entity.

After these large departures, FDI is only reaching around 660 million USD/year in 2023–24, indicating political turmoil and investor hesitancy. According to the Myanmar Investment Commission, cumulative investments are reported by countries in February 2025, which found that Singapore, China, and Thailand are the biggest investors in the MVC and Korea

sixth. The current study was finished in 2026 and used the full span of events from military rule through corporate responses post-coup.